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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D2.3 – Technical Requirements and Digital Ecosystem Architecture

Author(s):	Ioannis Tampakis, George Lalas, Dariya Rublova
Leading Partner:	Netcompany S.A.
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Report information

Purpose of the Report	This report outlines the technical requirements and system architecture for iDriving, translating user needs into technical specifications. It provides a foundation for the development, integration, and validation of all project components.		
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Relevant Task:	T2.5 Technical requirements specifications and ecosystem architecture		
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ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU's goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas of impact include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL
3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FUR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI.EIFFEL	FR
5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES
7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY

9	NETCOMPANY S.A.	INTRA	LU
10	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	RO
11	ALP.Lab GmbH	ALP.LAB	AT
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	AIM	RO
13	DRAXIS RESEARCH VENTURES ASTIKI MI EL KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA	DREVEN	EL
14	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION	LIF	BG
15	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS	THESSALONIKI	EL
16	GRAD KARLOVAC	COK	HR
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		Diana Gornea, Daniel Gherghiceanu, Lavinia Popa (SIMAVI), Vasileios Markantonakis (TUC), Zoi Dimitriadou (DREVEN), Irina Stipanovic (INFRA PLAN), Mohamed Berrazouane (ALP.LAB), Helena Korndoerfer (AUSTRIATECH)		
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Glossary

Acronym/Term	Full Name
AGL	Above Ground Level
API	Application Programming Interface
CMMS	Computerized Maintenance Management System
COCO	Common Objects in Context (dataset format)
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
D2.3	Deliverable 2.3
DB	Database
Docker	Containerization platform
DRM	Digital Rights Management
DT	Digital Twin
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EXIF	Exchangeable Image File Format
GFS	Global Forecast System
Git	Version Control System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MoSCoW	A prioritization technique for requirements
MPI	Message Passing Interface
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MTOM	Maximum Take-Off Mass
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics

RAM	Random Access Memory
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
REST	Representational State Transfer
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RTSP	Real-Time Streaming Protocol
SCC	Safety Criteria Catalogue
SRT	SubRip Subtitle (for video metadata)
SUMO	Simulation of Urban Mobility
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System (Drone)
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone)
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
VLC	Visible Light Communication
VLOS	Visual Line Of Sight
VMS	Variable Message Sign
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
VSS	Variable Speed Sign
WGS84	World Geodetic System 1984
WP	Work Package
WPS	WRF Preprocessing System
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting model
WRFDA	WRF Data Assimilation
XAI	Explainable Artificial Intelligence
XR	Extended Reality
YOLO	You Only Look Once (object detection algorithm)

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the technical requirements and digital ecosystem architecture for the iDriving platform, being developed within iDriving Horizon Europe project focused on advancing road safety and infrastructure management through digital innovation. Building upon the user needs and pilot scenarios established earlier in the project, this document defines the core functional requirements and provides a high-level architectural blueprint for the iDriving system.

The technical requirements are structured by major system building blocks and use case scenarios, ensuring traceability from stakeholder needs to concrete system components. The architecture follows the C4 Model, providing layered views from overall context to key software and hardware containers. This approach supports modularity, interoperability, and adaptability across diverse pilot sites.

The outputs of this deliverable form the foundation for the ongoing development, integration, and validation of the iDriving solution. As the project progresses, further refinement and expansion of requirements and architectural details will be informed by real-world feedback and emerging operational needs.

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the technical requirements and high-level digital ecosystem architecture for the iDriving platform. It is produced as part of Task 2.5 (“Technical requirements specifications and ecosystem architecture”) in Work Package 2, and builds directly on the user, safety, and ethical requirements defined in the deliverable D2.2.

The primary aim of the deliverable D2.3 is to translate stakeholder needs and pilot use case scenarios into concrete system-level requirements and a conceptual architecture that will guide all subsequent development, integration, and deployment activities. The document covers both functional and non-functional requirements, providing detailed specifications for each of the major system components to be implemented in WPs 3, 4, and 5.

As an intermediate step between user requirements and detailed technical design, this deliverable forms the foundation for the technical realization of the iDriving project and will be subject to further refinement as the project progresses, prototypes are developed, and feedback from pilot deployments is incorporated.

1.1 Deliverable context

As per the Grant Agreement, this deliverable represents the outcome of Task 2.5 (“Technical requirements specifications and ecosystem architecture”) aiming to define and document the following:

- Technical Requirements specifications
- iDriving Architecture, Specification of corresponding components

This deliverable provides the architectural details and the specifications of the iDRIVING software components as they are described and implemented in the following WPs and Tasks:

- WP3 / T3.1 – Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication
- WP3 / T3.2 – Intelligent Traffic Management System (ITMS)
- WP3 / T3.3 – Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings
- WP3 / T3.4 – Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks
- WP3 / T3.5 – Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance
- WP4 / T4.1 – Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
- WP4 / T4.2 – AI-Powered Behavioural analysis of objects of interest
- WP4 / T4.3 – Visual analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements

- WP4 / T4.4 – Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures
- WP4 / T4.5 – AI-driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring
- WP5 / T5.1 – Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning
- WP5 / T5.3 – Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems
- WP5 / T5.4 – Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies
- WP5 / T5.5 – Digital Twin-Based Control Center with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness.

1.2 Approach to defining the requirements

The technical requirements described herein were elicited through a multi-step, collaborative process involving all key consortium partners and relevant stakeholders. The process included:

- Analysis of user requirements and pilot scenarios, as documented in the deliverable D2.2.
- Thematic workshops and technical consultations with WP leaders and domain experts to identify, refine, and prioritize requirements.
- Circulation of requirements collection templates and iterative review cycles among partners.
- Mapping of requirements to specific use cases, system components, and technical tasks to ensure full traceability.
- Application of the MoSCoW prioritization method, categorizing requirements as must-have, should-have, could-have, or won't-have, to focus development on essential features and align with project constraints.

Throughout this process, attention was paid to legal, regulatory, and interoperability considerations, as well as to the anticipated evolution of requirements as pilots are executed and new insights are gained.

2 Overview of the iDriving system

2.1 System context and purpose

The iDriving system is designed in response to the pressing need for enhanced road safety and smarter management of urban and secondary rural road infrastructure across Europe. With road safety remaining a major societal challenge, iDriving aims to harness advances in digital technologies, ranging from edge AI to digital twins, to enable a data-driven, proactive approach to traffic monitoring, hazard detection, and infrastructure maintenance.

2.2 System Description and Main Capabilities

At its core, the iDriving system, presented in Figure 1, integrates a diverse set of hardware and software components into a cohesive platform supporting:

- **Real-time data acquisition** from sensors, cameras, UAVs (drones), weather stations, and connected vehicles
- **Edge computing** for immediate on-site processing and event detection
- **Centralized and federated data** for secure, policy-driven sharing of data assets
- **AI-driven analytics** for behavioural analysis, incident prediction, and risk assessment
- **Digital Twin technology** for real-time modelling of road environments, infrastructure, and traffic dynamics
- **Decision support tools** for operators and authorities, including maintenance planning and incident response
- **User-facing applications** providing alerts, notifications, and interactive feedback

Figure 1 - iDriving System Overview

This digital ecosystem enables seamless information flow among system components and stakeholders, supporting both centralized control and decentralized, on-site action.

2.3 Summary of use cases, scenarios, and user requirements

The following sub-chapters provide an overview of the six use cases, including scenario descriptions and user requirements.

2.3.1 Use Case 1.1: Graz, Austria

Table 1 - Use Case 1.1: Graz, Austria

Scenario Title	Description
Congestion Prediction and Dynamic Re-routing	Continuous monitoring of traffic flow is conducted using various sensors and AI-enabled cameras. Predictive models analyse real-time and historical data to forecast congestion. Based on these predictions, alternative routes are communicated to road users via VMS and mobile or In-vehicle applications to optimize traffic distribution.

Automated Detection of Road User Violations	Video analytics systems automatically detect violations such as non-usage of helmets or seatbelts, traffic light infractions, and unauthorized lane usage, including wrong way driving or improper use of turning lanes. Identified violations are documented for road operators and communicated to relevant road users in order to increase compliance.
Safety-Critical Incidents Detection	The system continuously analyses sensors and video data to identify dangerous or critical situations. Upon detection, immediate alerts are issued to road users and road operators to enable prompt intervention and minimize potential risks.

2.3.2 Use Case 1.2: Nevers, France

Table 2 - Use Case 1.2: Nevers, France

Scenario title	Description
Deployment of Monitoring systems	Install cameras at key locations like intersections, parking zones, and zebra crossings, while deploying UAVs over critical areas, including bicycle lanes and pedestrian-heavy zones, to provide a comprehensive ground and aerial view of roads
Real Time integration and analysis	Integrate ground camera and UAV data into iDriving's Digital Twin, using AI to analyse traffic patterns, detect infractions, identify risky behaviours, and highlight areas for infrastructure improvements.
Communication and alerts to road users	Activate messaging on road or online systems to alert road users of potential incidents. Notify drivers approaching zebra crossings to yield via VMS or in-vehicle messages. Use VLC for communication and warn distracted cyclists to enhance compliance and safety.

2.3.3 Use Case 2.1: Karlovac, Croatia

Table 3 - Use Case 2.1: Karlovac, Croatia

Scenario title	Description
Detection of road damages (potholes, cracks)	Deploy several technologies to support inspection procedure: data collection using cameras on inspection vehicles, fixed cameras on critical sections, like intersections or sections with heavy traffic, and UAVs over remote areas. Environmental monitoring using smart weather stations, to correlate road damages occurrence.
Provide maintenance plan to infrastructure managers for repair of detected potholes	Develop DT-based optimized model for maintenance plan while considering traffic flow (cameras and traffic counters data) and weather forecast (weather station)
Communication and alerts to road users before and during maintenance works	Activate messaging on road or online systems to alert road users of maintenance road activities. Notify drivers approaching road work zones to yield via VMS or in-vehicle messages. Use VLC for communication and warn distracted cyclists to enhance compliance and safety.
Monitor workers safety during maintenance works	Deploy UAV during the maintenance works to detect any safety violations in the work zone areas

2.3.4 Use Case 2.2: Thessaloniki, Greece

Table 4 - Use Case 2.2: Thessaloniki, Greece

Scenario title	Description
Accumulating water from rainfall/ Gusty winds	Advanced weather stations monitor weather data. Data analysed to identify patterns indicating potential road hazards, such as water accumulation that could lead to slippery conditions or flooding or strong winds for two wheelers. In-vehicle warning application, digital road signs, and the dedicated iDriving mobile application all start issuing alerts and inform on alternative routes. Traffic manager is informed
Fallen Trees/Rockslides	UAVs fly autonomously patrolling the risk areas to detect obstacles on the road like fallen trees or rocks. Existence of obstacles on the road

	leads to warning to iDriving platform. Warning applications and digital road signs all start issuing alerts and inform on alternative routes. Traffic manager is informed
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2.3.5 Use Case 3.1: Alba Iulia, Romania

Table 5 - Use Case 3.1: Alba Iulia, Romania

Scenario title	Description
Aggressive Driving Detection	<p>Detection of aggressive behaviour in traffic (e.g., sudden lane changes, rapid acceleration/deceleration).</p> <p>The scenario implies using video cameras with video analytics to identify risky behaviours, (e.g., traffic sensors to detect sudden lane changes and hard braking,) dedicated Traffic Management Centre platform for analysing and processing alerts.</p>
Speeding detection	<p>Real-time speeding detection using smart cameras and speed cameras</p> <p>The scenario implies using video cameras for vehicle identification, smart radars for speed measurement, platform dedicated to the existing Traffic Management System in Alba Iulia, mobile application for near real-time user notification.</p> <p>The scenario targets speed over the legal limit detection, automatically generating alerts for drivers and sending them via the mobile app, analysis of collected data to identify high-risk areas, implementation of proactive measures to optimize traffic flow (traffic light adjustment)</p>
Speeding and Aggressive Driving Detection	<p>Combining detection of excessive speed and aggressive behaviour to provide a complete traffic risk monitoring solution.</p> <p>The scenario implies using video cameras and smart radars for speed and aggressive behaviour detection, traffic sensors to monitor sudden lane changes and dangerous braking, dedicated platform for traffic management system in Alba</p>

	<p>Iulia, mobile application for near real-time alerts and notifications.</p> <p>The scenario targets simultaneous detection of excessive speeding and aggressive behaviour, driver notification via VMS panels and mobile app.</p> <p>Creating heat maps to identify high-risk areas.</p>
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2.3.6 Use Case 3.2: Bizkaia, Spain

Table 6 - Use Case 2.3: Bizkaia, Spain

Scenario title	Description
Real-time detection	iDriving sensors installed in one of the vehicles involved in the accident detect and report the sudden stop. Other drivers in the area, using the iDriving in-vehicle or the mobile app, confirm the accident.
Deployment of Monitoring systems	Cameras installed, and UAVs dispatched over the area provide a comprehensive view of the situation, covering both ground and aerial perspectives.
Digital twin generation	NeRFs and visual analysis create an accurate 3D model of the zone. This real-time data is shared with local authorities, providing a virtual replication.
Rerouting and planning	Using historical traffic data and real-time input, iDriving’s algorithms determine the fastest route for emergency vehicles and the alternative routes for approaching drivers.
Real-time alerts	Through the mobile app, users are informed about the alternative routes, while VMS suggest slowing down within the area.

3 Technical requirements

This section presents the iDriving technical requirements, grouped according to their scope and relationship to the project’s work structure. Unlike a strict split between functional and non-functional requirements, our approach is as follows:

- **General Non-Functional Requirements** are listed in a dedicated section. These capture cross-cutting quality attributes that apply to the system, such as real-time performance, interoperability, access control, usability, data protection, and compliance. These are identified with the format TR-NFUN-GEN-y, where y is a running index for general non-functional requirements.
- **Work Package-Specific Requirements** are then detailed per Work Package (WP). For each WP, we present both functional and non-functional requirements together, reflecting the practical integration of quality attributes and system functionalities in the project’s implementation. Requirements here are labelled as follows:
 - TR-FUN-x-y for functional requirements, where x is the WP number and y is the index within that WP.
 - TR-NFUN-x-y for non-functional requirements specific to a WP, following the same numbering logic.

This structure ensures that both types of requirements, functional (what the system does) and non-functional (how the system performs or must behave), are addressed in direct connection to the responsible project areas and tools. It also makes clear which requirements apply project-wide and which are WP-specific.

The set of requirements can evolve during the project, due to e.g. an update of the user requirements. This may lead to additional requirements, which can be assigned consecutive higher numbers or already existing numbers with lowercase letters appended (e.g. ...-1a), or to some requirements being dropped, without renumbering of the full set.

3.1 Functional & Non-Functional requirements

3.1.1 General Non-Functional requirements

ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-1
Name (Optional)	Real-Time Performance
Description	Critical alerts, safety processing, and control functions must operate with real-time or near real-time latency
Category	Performance

Related Tasks	T3.2, T3.3, T4.1, T4.2, T5.5
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Performance testing, simulation
Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-2
Name (Optional)	Interoperability via Standard Formats
Description	All tools must exchange data using open, well-defined formats (JSON, CSV, etc.) with schemas.
Category	Interoperability
Related Tasks	All
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Integration testing, schema validation
Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-3
Name (Optional)	Access Control
Description	The platform must provide role-based access to functions (e.g., admin/operator), with clear separation of privileges.
Category	Security, Design
Related Tasks	All
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have

Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Access control testing, role simulation
Comments	E.g. Admin, operator, and user roles.
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-4
Name (Optional)	Usability for Critical UIs
Description	Mobile, infotainment, and operator UIs must comply with usability standards (e.g., non-distraction, ISO 15005), and be tested with end users.
Category	Usability, Design
Related Tasks	T3.3, T5.5
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Usability testing, surveys,
Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-5
Name (Optional)	Input Data Quality
Description	All image/video inputs must have $\geq 1080p$ resolution and ≥ 5 fps frame rate for accurate detection.
Category	Data Quality
Related Tasks	T3.4, T4.1
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Data validation

Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-6
Name (Optional)	Hardware Compatibility
Description	All edge processing modules must be deployable on an embedded device such as a NVIDIA Jetson
Category	Compatibility
Related Tasks	T4.1
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Deployment testing on Jetson
Comments	Required for field deployment
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-7
Name (Optional)	Network Connectivity
Description	The system must maintain an active internet connection to ensure real-time processing and communication.
Category	Availability
Related Tasks	All
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	-
Comments	Applies to UAVs, edge devices, server comms.
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-8
Name (Optional)	Camera Field of View

Description	Cameras must be installed to maximize field of view and optimize for the detection algorithm's needs.
Category	Deployment, Quality
Related Tasks	T4.1, T4.2
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	Field validation, sample checks
Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-GEN-9
Name (Optional)	Data Protection and Ethical Compliance
Description	The system shall handle all detection operations and data processing in accordance with GDPR requirements and established AI ethics principles (e.g., fairness, transparency, accountability).
Category	Security, Privacy, Ethics
Related Tasks	All
Related Tool	All
Related Use Cases	All
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Applicable GDPR regulations; AI Ethics Frameworks (e.g., EU AI Act)
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	-
Comments	This NFR ensures that any collection, processing, or analysis of personal data respects user privacy rights and that AI-driven operations remain fair, transparent, and accountable.
	iDriving technical requirement specification
ID	TR-FUN-3.1-1
Name (Optional)	Data Catalog Publication, Policy Negotiation, Data Access

Description	User interface to describe the Data Catalog, to search for Data Catalogs within a Data Space and to trigger and monitor policy negotiation and data sharing.
Category	Functional, Design, Security
Related Tasks	T3.1: Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication
Related Tool	Tekniker Dataspace Connector
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1 Graz, Austria; UC 1.2 Nevers, France; UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia; UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece; UC 3.1 Alba Iulia, Romania; UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	Data Catalog Description
Verification Method	Usability Testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-3.1-2
Name (Optional)	Data Sharing
Description	The service should share data from different data sources to different processing tools.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T3.1: Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication
Related Tool	Tekniker Dataspace Connector
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1 Graz, Austria; UC 1.2 Nevers, France; UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia; UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece; UC 3.1 Alba Iulia, Romania; UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Data Sources
Input Needed	Data Sources
Verification Method	Integration testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-3.2-1
Name (Optional)	Route guidance tool

Description	The system identifies alternative routes for given origin-destination and vehicle type, based on actual traffic data and identified incident(s) affecting circulation in specific roads. The aim is to improve safety and efficiency of trips of all vehicle types.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T3.2: Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows
Related Tool	SUMO microscopic traffic simulator
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1 Graz, Austria; UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia; UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece; UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	SUMO urban network model, travel demand, initial traffic signal plan
Input Needed	weather & incident alerts detection (type, location, time), traffic information (speed or density or flow per link), O-D trips to reroute
Verification Method	Alternative scenarios simulation in SUMO
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-3.2-2
Name (Optional)	Dynamic signal control tool
Description	The system provides dynamic adjustment of traffic light timing for the identified (controlled) intersection(s) based on real-time traffic information stemming from the neighbouring roads (links). The strategy aims to improve efficiency of the trips served by the intersection(s).
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T3.2: Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows
Related Tool	SUMO microscopic traffic simulator
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1 Graz, Austria;
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	SUMO urban network model, travel demand, initial traffic signal plan

Input Needed	Measurements or estimates of queue lengths or accumulated vehicles for all incoming/outgoing links of the controlled intersection during last signal cycle, turn ratios
Verification Method	Alternative scenarios simulation in SUMO
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-3.3-1
Name (Optional)	Interface for mobile/infotainment system
Description	The system shall provide a user interface adapted for mobile devices and vehicle infotainment system, with a user-friendly design and notifications
Category	Functional, Design, interoperability, security, regulatory/compliance
Related Tasks	T3.3 Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings
Related Tool	Mobile Application, In-vehicle Application
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Interface depends on the device performance Data received from the other components (centralized at server level)
Input Needed	-User requirements list
Verification Method	Usability testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-3.3-2
Name (Optional)	Alerting and communication service
Description	The system shall provide a dedicated service for sending and receiving messages to and from the main server, including the handling of notifications and alerts such as C-ITS messages
Category	Functional, Performance, interoperability, security, regulatory/compliance
Related Tasks	T3.3 Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings
Related Tool	Mobile Application, In-vehicle Application
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2.
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have

Dependencies	Internet Connection
Input Needed	Data schema definitions of the messages
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-3.4.1
Name (Optional)	Payload Capability
Description	The payload selected for each mission must not exceed the maximum payload weight available for the drone. This weight includes both the payload itself, and all the necessary equipment required for attachment to the UAV.
Category	Non-Functional, Performance, Design, Equipment
Related Tasks	T3.4, T3.5, T4.1, T4.3, T4.5.
Related Tool	iDriving Mission UAV
Related Use Cases	Spain, Austria, Greece, Croatia, France
MoSCoW Scale	Must Have
Dependencies	In the scope of the project the sensor will depend on the defined user requirements.
Input Needed	The required input consists of the minimum technical specifications of the developed tools—such as those related to photo and video analysis—which are essential for effectively selecting the most appropriate sensor and ensuring that the chosen sensor meets the required standards.
Verification Method	Test multiple data sets captured by the sensors using the developed tools.
Comments	Suggested sensor for integrating on the UAV (One of the following): SIYI A8 mini Zoom Gimbal Camera ZT6 Mini Dual-Sensor Optical Pod The AI developers need to verify that the technical specifications of the proposed sensors are sufficient for their developments.
ID	TR-FUN-3.4.2
Name (Optional)	AI Algorithms
Description	In case of near real time processing, the AI algorithms developed for this UAV must be tailored to meet the specifications of the on-board processor or the ground control station.

Category	Functional, Performance, interoperability.
Related Tasks	T3.4, T3.5, T4.1, T4.3, T4.5.
Related Tool	iDriving Mission UAV
Related Use Cases	Spain, Austria, Greece, Croatia, France
MoSCoW Scale	Must Have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	The AI algorithms must be pre-installed on the onboard processor or the ground control station before the demonstrations.
Verification Method	Rigorous testing prior of the demonstrations.
Comments	<p>Remote Access for installing all the required components will be granted from ACCELIGENCE.</p> <p>For the pilot use cases, and in scenarios requiring the execution of AI algorithms in near real-time, the following two approaches are available:</p> <p>Onboard processing with an NVIDIA AI-oriented computer mounted on the UAV.</p> <p>Ground station processing: The video stream can be transmitted in real-time to a ground station computer, where the AI algorithms will be installed and executed. The resulting data can then be transferred to any required cloud or server.</p> <p>Benefits of the second approach: Easier troubleshooting Stable connectivity, as the processor remains in a fixed location Greater computational resources – ground systems can support more powerful hardware, enabling complex AI models to run more efficiently Reduced payload weight – resulting in increased flight time</p> <p>Suggested onboard processor for integrating on the UAV:</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">NVIDIA Jetson Nano Dev Kit</p> <p>Suggested ground station for executing AI on the ground:</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Laptop: NVidia rtx 3050 CPU i7 Ram 16gb Nvme 4g</p>

	The AI developers need to verify that the technical specifications of the proposed sensors are sufficient for their developments.
ID	TR-FUN-3.4.3
Name (Optional)	Autonomous Navigation
Description	The ability to know and define set waypoints and preprogrammed flight paths is important for uploading the required flight paths to the UAV for executing automated missions.
Category	Functional, Performance, interoperability.
Related Tasks	T3.4, T3.5.
Related Tool	iDriving Mission UAV, UAV-based Path Planning for Coverage Operations
Related Use Cases	Spain, Austria, Greece, Croatia, France
MoSCoW Scale	Must Have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	In case of autonomous flights – a predetermined flight plan is required.
Verification Method	Rigorous testing prior of the demonstrations by uploading and executing multiple autonomous missions extracted by the developed software
Comments	-
ID	TR-NFUN-3.4.4
Name (Optional)	Available network.
Description	Available network (4G, 5G, WiFi) for data transmission in real time is required.
Category	Non-Functional, interoperability.
Related Tasks	T3.4. Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks
Related Tool	iDriving Mission UAV
Related Use Cases	Spain, Austria, Greece, Croatia, France
MoSCoW Scale	Must Have
Dependencies	The area where the demonstrations will be executed needs to have network coverage.

Input Needed	For real time communication and live data transmission network is required.
Verification Method	-
Comments	ACCELI can provide a 4G stick that can be connected to the ground station or directly to the drone, providing the network required for transmitting data to the cloud, if needed. This requirement is a task-specific extension of TR-NFUN-GEN-7."
ID	TR-NFUN-3.4.5
Name (Optional)	Compliance with Regulations
Description	The UAV must comply with EASA regulations in the Open Category A1/A3, namely: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximum Take-off Mass (MTOM): Drones in this subcategory can have a maximum weight of 25 kilograms. • No Fly Zones: Flying is prohibited over open-air assemblies of people (e.g., concerts, festivals) and densely populated areas with more than 300 people per square meter. • Visual Line of Sight (VLOS): The pilot must always maintain visual contact with the drone during the flight. • Maximum Altitude: Drones cannot fly above 120 meters above ground level (AGL) unless a special authorization is obtained.
Category	Non-Functional, Regulatory/compliance
Related Tasks	T3.4. Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks
Related Tool	iDriving Mission UAV
Related Use Cases	Spain, Austria, Greece, Croatia, France
MoSCoW Scale	Must Have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	All required flight authorizations must be provided by the end users to the ACCELI team to conduct the missions over their designated areas.
Verification Method	-
Comments	-

ID	TR-FUN-3.5-1
Name (Optional)	Mission Area Definition
Description	The service shall accept as input a geographical area defined as a polygon in WGS84 coordinates, including information about possible no-fly zones and/or obstacles. This input will define the spatial boundaries and constraints of the mission area, which will be used to inform and constrain UAV path planning and mission execution.
Category	Functional, Design, Regulatory/Compliance
Related Tasks	T3.5. Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance
Related Tool	UAV-based Path Planning for Coverage Operations
Related Use Cases	UC 1.2 Nevers, France/ UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia/ UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece/ UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Geospatial data availability, Internet Connection
Input Needed	WGS84 polygon, list of obstacles/no-fly-zones (if applicable)
Verification Method	Unit and integration testing; input parsing validation
Comments	Foundational for initiating the mission planning process
ID	TR-FUN-3.5-2
Name (Optional)	Single-UAV Coverage Path Planning
Description	The service shall compute an optimal coverage path for a single UAV to map/monitor a specified area, considering any obstacles, no-fly zones within the operational area.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T3.5. Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance
Related Tool	UAV-based Path Planning for Coverage Operations
Related Use Cases	UC 1.2 Nevers, France/ UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia/ UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece/ UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	TR-FUN-3.5-1, UAV availability, specifications and capabilities, Internet Connection

Input Needed	UAVs characteristics i.e., Battery level, Maximum flight time, Maximum – Minimum altitude for safety and legal constraints, Maximum speed, Payload (camera/FoV) specs
Verification Method	Simulated mission coverage verification
Comments	Ensures mission execution for mapping/monitoring an area of interest
ID	TR-FUN-3.5-3
Name (Optional)	Multi-UAV Coverage Path Planning
Description	The service shall compute cooperative paths for a swarm of UAVs to cooperatively map/monitor a specified area, considering any obstacles, no-fly zones within the operational area.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T3.5. Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance
Related Tool	UAV-based Path Planning for Coverage Operations
Related Use Cases	UC 1.2 Nevers, France/ UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia/ UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece/ UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Multiple UAVs, Internet Connection
Input Needed	Number of UAVs, UAVs characteristics i.e., Battery level, Maximum flight time, Maximum – Minimum altitude for safety and legal constraints, Maximum speed, Payload (camera/FoV) specs
Verification Method	Simulated mission coverage verification
Comments	Ensures distributed mission execution across available UAVs for mapping/monitoring an area of interest
ID	TR-NFUN-3.5-4
Name (Optional)	Data Interoperability
Description	The system shall support standardized data formats for mission inputs/outputs, such as .JSON for area definitions and waypoint extraction.
Category	Interoperability
Related Tasks	T3.5. Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance
Related Tool	UAV-based Path Planning for Coverage Operations

Related Use Cases	UC 1.2 Nevers, France/ UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia/ UC 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece/ UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Internet Connection
Input Needed	Data schema definitions
Verification Method	Integration testing
Comments	<p>Only the output will be tested through integration testing against the defined data schema. The input will be inserted through the platform that will be developed under Task 3.5, which will act as the interface for mission area and parameter definitions.</p> <p>This requirement operationalizes TR-NFUN-GEN-2 for UAV mission planning.</p>

3.1.2 Requirements related to WP4

ID	TR-NFUN-4.1-1
Name (Optional)	Jetson NVIDIA Platform
Description	T4.1 will be implemented on an embedded device, such as the NVIDIA Jetson platform
Category	Equipment
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	-
Related Use Cases	UC1.1/ UC1.2/ U.C. 2.2./U.C 3.2
MoSCoW Scale	-
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	-
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-1
Name (Optional)	Seatbelt detection.

Description	The system shall execute an object detection algorithm on embedded devices connected to roadside cameras or UAVs to identify and classify seat belt usage.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Seatbelt detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1-Graz, Austria
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Dependence on a dataset containing images of drivers both wearing and not wearing seatbelts for training the deep learning model. Camera's field of view and angle
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on a provided sample, as part of integration testing
Comments	Provided data or video samples from different angles are crucial for the functionality of the tool. Most of the images in the current model are captured from road cameras at a 45-degree angle and not from a long distance. Depending on the integration and the placement of the cameras, we may need data to retrain the model from that specific point of view.
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-2
Name (Optional)	Mobile detection.
Description	The system shall execute an object detection algorithm on embedded devices connected to road cameras or UAVs to identify and classify mobile phone usage.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Mobile detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1-Graz, Austria/ UC 1.2-Nevers, France
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model Camera's field of view and angle

Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on a provided sample, as part of integration testing
Comments	Provided data or video samples from different angles are crucial for the functionality of the tool. Most of the images in the current model are captured from road cameras at a 45-degree angle and not from a long distance. Depending on the integration and placement of the cameras, we may need data to retrain the model from that specific point of view. In UC 1.2, detecting bikers using mobile phones requires a dedicated dataset. However, we were unable to find any suitable dataset. If such a dataset can be provided, then this tool can also be integrated into UC 1.2.
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-3
Name (Optional)	Helmet Detection
Description	The system shall execute an object detection algorithm on embedded devices to verify helmet usage by riders of bicycles and motorcycles
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Helmet detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1-Graz, Austria/ UC1.2-Nevers, France
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model Camera's field of view and angle
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on a provided sample, as part of integration testing
Comments	Provided data or video samples from different angles are crucial for the functionality of the tool. Most of the images in the current model are captured from road cameras at a 45-degree angle and not from a long distance. Depending on the integration and the placement of the cameras, we may need data to retrain the model from that specific point of view.

ID	TR-FUN-4.1-4
Name (Optional)	License Plate Detection
Description	The system shall execute an object detection algorithm on embedded devices to identify the license plates of offenders who are not wearing seatbelts or helmets, or who are using mobile phones while driving.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	License plate detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1-Graz, Austria/ UC1.2-Nevers, France
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model Camera's field of view and angle
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on a provided sample, as part of integration testing
Comments	The model has been trained on a dataset containing close-up images. Additionally, images from street cameras were included to help generalize the model. However, due to the small size of license plates, it may be difficult to detect and read them from drone footage. For accurate license plate recognition, the image must be clear enough to distinguish the characters.
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-5
Name (Optional)	Count Cars
Description	The system shall detect and count the number of cars present in each video frame captured by connected cameras.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Count Car detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 1.1-Graz, Austria, UC2.2-Thessaloniki, Greece
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model

	Camera's field of view and angle Provision of data
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on provided samples, as part of integration testing
Comments	This tool was added later, following the plenary meeting in Graz. Provided data or video samples from different angles are crucial for the functionality of the tool. Most of the images in the current model are captured from road cameras at a 45-degree angle and not from a long distance. Depending on the integration and the placement of the cameras, we may need data to retrain the model from that specific point of view.
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-6
Name (Optional)	Zebra crossing detection
Description	The system shall detect the presence of zebra crossings in video frames captured by road cameras or UAVs.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Zebra Crossing detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 1.2. - Nevers, France
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model Camera's field of view and angle Provision of data
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on provided samples, as part of integration testing
Comments	This tool was added following a bilateral meeting with TEKNIKER for T4.2. The purpose is to determine whether a person is walking on a zebra crossing or not – similar to checking if someone is walking on sidewalk. If needed CERTH will provide only the coordinates of the zebra crossing, by combining the zebra crossing coordinates within the frame with the detected position of the person. We can assess

	<p>whether the individual is walking on the street or within the designed crossing area.</p> <p>Sidewalk detection is not feasible, as most pavements require polygon-shaped annotations to be accurately bounded. However, our current models only support rectangular bounding boxes. Training a model to handle both rectangular and polygon annotation is not supported within our framework, Therefore, only zebra crossing can be detected, given that the provided dataset includes rectangular bounding box annotations.</p>
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-7
Name (Optional)	Fallen Tree and Rockslide detection tool
Description	The system shall execute an object detection algorithm on embedded devices to monitor landscapes and roadways for fallen trees and rockslides using video feeds from UAVs. It analyses aerial imagery to quickly identify and assess potential hazards.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Disaster detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC2.2 - Thessaloniki, Greece
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	<p>Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model</p> <p>Camera's field of view and angle</p> <p>Provision of data</p>
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on provided samples, as part of integration testing
Comments	It is important to provide us with data from the field of interest that includes the relevant objects of interest
ID	TR-FUN-4.1-8
Name (Optional)	Crashed car detection tool
Description	The system shall execute an object detection algorithm on embedded devices to identify crashed vehicles in real time using video feeds from CCTV cameras or UAVs. It analyses the imagery to detect unusually stationary vehicles or collisions on the road and promptly alerts emergency services.

Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.1 - Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring
Related Tool	Crashed Car detection tool
Related Use Cases	UC 3.2 - Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Dependence on existing datasets for training the deep learning model Camera's field of view and angle Provision of data
Input Needed	Frames or videos with high frame rate
Verification Method	Training the deep learning model, and performing inference on provided samples, as part of integration testing
Comments	It is important to provide us with data from the relevant field that includes the objects of interest.
ID	TR-FUN-4.2-1
Name (Optional)	Red light violation detector
Description	Detect vehicles in real-time and determine if they cross a virtual stop line during a red traffic light phase.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Task 4.2
Related Tool	Red Light Violation Detector
Related Use Cases	UR_UC1.1_17
MoSCoW Scale	Should-have
Dependencies	Real-time video input stream, accurate traffic light state data, correct virtual line configuration.
Input Needed	Video stream from surveillance cameras, real-time traffic light status data. Obtaining this information does not appear to be feasible. It cannot be acquired through computer vision, and it is currently unclear whether access to the traffic light timing data will be possible for the intended use case.
Verification Method	System validation with test video sequences including known violation cases; cross-verification of alerts and captured evidence (image + timestamp + traffic light status).

Comments	The solution supports hybrid (edge-cloud) architectures. Evidence is saved for enforcement purposes. Implementation primarily in Python.
ID	TR-FUN-4.2-2
Name (Optional)	Improper Lane Usage Detection
Description	Analyse vehicle trajectories in real-time to detect deviations from assigned lanes or intrusions into restricted zones using object detection, tracking, and spatial reasoning.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.2
Related Tool	Improper Lane Usage Detector
Related Use Cases	UR_UC1.1_15 (Graz), UR_UC1.2_4 (Nevers)
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	Real-time video input, preconfigured lane zone maps, continuous vehicle tracking data.
Input Needed	Video stream from urban surveillance cameras, lane zone configuration data.
Verification Method	Evaluation with annotated video sequences comparing vehicle paths against allowed lane zones; verification through generated alerts and evidence (image + timestamp + ID + lane info).
Comments	Primarily implemented in Python. Deployment can be on-premises or hybrid (edge-cloud). Docker-compatible deployment is recommended. Vehicle IDs should be anonymized in public-facing alerts if required by regulations.
ID	TR-FUN-4.2-3
Name (Optional)	Pedestrian Violation Detection Outside Zebra Crossing
Description	The system shall detect when a pedestrian crosses or walks outside the spatial boundaries of a zebra crossing by analysing the pedestrian's tracked position relative to the segmented zebra crossing area.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.2
Related Tool	Zebra Crossing Violation Detector
Related Use Cases	UC1.2
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have

Dependencies	Requires reliable pedestrian detection and tracking; Requires accurate zebra crossing segmentation; Needs calibrated camera perspective and zebra crossing geometry
Input Needed	Video stream from surveillance cameras; Zebra crossing mask (configurable via JSON/image/admin GUI)
Verification Method	Functional tests on real or simulated video footage; Validation of detection accuracy against manually annotated ground truth; Testing alert generation and log storage for detected violations
Comments	Critical for ensuring pedestrian safety monitoring; Integration with external systems (e.g., alerting authorities) can be achieved via REST/MQTT APIs; Evidence management requires secure access control.
ID	TR-FUN-4.2-4
Name (Optional)	Detection of Anomalous Driving Behaviour
Description	The system shall analyse real-time vehicle sensor data (accelerometer, gyroscope, GPS) to identify driving anomalies such as sudden acceleration, harsh braking, abrupt steering, and irregular trajectories.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T4.2
Related Tool	Anomaly Driving Behaviour Detector
Related Use Cases	UR_UC3.1_1 (Alba Iulia), UR_UC3.1_2 (Alba Iulia), UR_UC3.1_3 (Alba Iulia)
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Requires continuous and synchronized sensor data streams (accelerometer, gyroscope, GPS); Needs pre-trained models or statistical methods for anomaly detection
Input Needed	Real-time sensor data (acceleration, angular velocity, GPS coordinates); Speed limit information (optional, for speed violations)
Verification Method	Controlled test drives with known anomaly patterns; Comparison with ground truth labels; Offline validation with labelled datasets; Real-time system monitoring logs
Comments	Critical for detecting dangerous or erratic vehicle behaviours; Must support timestamp synchronization to ensure accurate event detection; Can be extended with external data (e.g., speed limits, road types)

ID	TR-FUN-4.3-1
Name (Optional)	Road Infrastructure Defect Dataset Collection
Description	This tool will utilize a deep learning algorithm to detect road defects. A dedicated dataset should be prepared for each type of defect to ensure accurate identification and analysis.
Category	e.g. Functional, Design
Related Tasks	TASK 4.3: Visual analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements
Related Tool	Defect Detector and Severity Assessment
Related Use Cases	UC 2.1 Karlovac
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	To enable the tool to detect each type of defect, a dedicated dataset must be created. Each defect type should include a minimum of 300 images per defect type (a higher number of samples improves performance), captured under varying conditions such as lighting, angles, shooting environments, and backgrounds. Separate datasets should be prepared for significantly different input sources, such as dash cameras and drones, to ensure accuracy. Lastly, the datasets must be formatted in YOLOv11 and COCO Segmentation standard.
Input Needed	Dataset with the desired classes for training
Verification Method	By training the deep learning model and inference on some provided sample
Comments	The availability of datasets for each defect type is crucial for the functionality of the tool. Without these datasets, the tool cannot accurately identify road defects. If the datasets are unavailable, we can explore frugal or augmentation techniques as part of our mitigation strategy.
ID	TR-FUN-4.3-2
Name (Optional)	Processing Pipeline Requirements for Visual Media Input and Output
Description	The tool processes images or videos as input and outputs annotations with bounding boxes marking detected defects. The images can be sourced from various devices, such as mobile phones, dash cameras, traffic surveillance systems, or drones. To ensure accurate detection and seamless system functionality, specific requirements must be satisfied.
Category	Functional, Design, Interoperability, Equipment

Related Tasks	TASK 4.3: Visual analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements
Related Tool	Defect Detector and Severity Assessment
Related Use Cases	UC 2.1 Karlovac
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	<p>TR-FUN-4.3-1 The input should be similar to the datasets, for better accuracy, NVIDIA GPU at least 3090 for inference, Camera source type,</p> <p>Images and videos must be sharp and have a resolution of at least Full HD. Drone images should be captured from a maximum height of 15 meters. Accepted file formats are JPEG and PNG for images, and MP4 for videos (at least 25fps). Each image must include geographic coordinates embedded in the EXIF metadata, while videos should have geographic coordinates in .SRT subtitle format, mapped to each frame. The tool will output annotations with bounding boxes highlighting defect locations, along with equivalent textual data delivered in a pre-defined JSON format for integration with other tools.</p> <p>The images or videos can be accessed either from a storage server or via an RTSP stream. In both cases, it is essential to include metadata, such as GPS coordinates.</p> <p>The annotated image results should be saved on a storage server.</p>
Input Needed	Images or videos in the appropriate format
Verification Method	Parsing validation, integration testing
Comments	The input type, metadata, and output format of the tool are crucial for optimizing its performance and ensuring seamless integration with other systems.
ID	TR-FUN-4.4-1
Name (Optional)	WRF Forecasting and Data Assimilation Stack
Description	The system shall support weather forecasting using WRF and data assimilation via WRFDA, including multi-domain nesting and integration of observational data.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	TASK 4.4: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures
Related Tool	Tool 4.4.1: Weather Prediction Tool using WRF and Data Assimilation

Related Use Cases	UC2.2 - Thessaloniki, Greece / UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Git, Docker, MPI, NetCDF, WRF, WPS, WRFDA, observational input sources
Input Needed	Static geographical data, meteorological input (e.g., GFS), observational data, domain configuration
Verification Method	Comparison of assimilated vs. non-assimilated forecasts, runtime consistency, performance benchmarks
Comments	Assimilated outputs should be validated using ground truth weather station data.
ID	TR-NFUN-4.4-2
Name (Optional)	WRF Forecasting and Data Assimilation Stack containerization
Description	The forecasting stack shall be fully containerized using Docker, encapsulating all dependencies, and automating the complete forecasting workflow.
Category	Non-Functional, Deployment
Related Tasks	TASK 4.4: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures
Related Tool	Tool 4.4.1: Weather Prediction Tool using WRF and Data Assimilation
Related Use Cases	UC2.2 - Thessaloniki, Greece / UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Git, Docker, MPI, NetCDF, WRF, WPS, WRFDA, observational input sources
Input Needed	-
Verification Method	-
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-4.4-3
Name (Optional)	API-based Data Ingestion
Description	A service shall be implemented to request, parse, and store weather data from open and proprietary APIs.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	TASK 4.4: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures

Related Tool	Tool 4.4.1: Weather Prediction Tool using WRF and Data Assimilation
Related Use Cases	UC2.2 - Thessaloniki, Greece / UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Docker, Git, API availability
Input Needed	APIs documentation, authentication credentials
Verification Method	Not applicable
Comments	All APIs should be active to import data.
ID	TR-FUN-4.4-4
Name (Optional)	Forecast Output Validator
Description	The system shall verify and validate forecast outputs (e.g., precipitation, temperature, RH) against observational ground truth data to ensure accuracy and reliability.
Category	Functional, Interoperability
Related Tasks	TASK 4.4: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures
Related Tool	Tool 4.4.1: Weather Prediction Tool using WRF and Data Assimilation
Related Use Cases	UC2.2 - Thessaloniki, Greece / UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Ground truth data availability, defined accuracy thresholds
Input Needed	Model outputs (e.g., wrfout files), observational datasets
Verification Method	Statistical comparison (e.g. MAE, RMSE, bias), graphical diagnostics
Comments	
ID	TR-FUN-4.4-5
Name (Optional)	AI-Based Alert System
Description	The system shall make forecast data and station measurements accessible for specific areas, and an automated process (via cron) shall evaluate whether predefined hazard thresholds are met. The results shall then be fed into an AI system (LLM), which generates alerts that include risk levels and relevant weather data. These alerts shall be made available through an API on the iDriving platform.
Category	Functional

Related Tasks	TASK 4.4: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures
Related Tool	Tool 4.4.2: Weather Prediction Tool using WRF and Data Assimilation
Related Use Cases	UC2.2 - Thessaloniki, Greece / UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Git, docker, Web Framework (like Django Rest Framework), Relational Database, either locally installed Open Source LLM or Cloud Provided LLM (Accessed via API), Python
Input Needed	Station Real Time Data, Forecast Data, Use Case data
Verification Method	User Feedback
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-4.5-1
Name (Optional)	3D Reconstruction of Road Environments
Description	The tool transforms 2D visual data captured by UAVs or ground-based moving cameras in road environments into 3D representations, enhancing safety, enabling remote inspections, and providing valuable maintenance insights. The scale of the scene extended from a single defect in a small-scale scene to a larger partition of the road representing broader environments. The reconstruction method must be adapted according to the scale of the scene, whether it is a localized defect or a larger road segment. Also, the tool reconstructs scenes with enriched information, enhancing scene understanding and highlighting potential road defects in 3D space.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T4.5 AI-driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring
Related Tool	3D-Smart Tool
Related Use Cases	UC 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High quality visual data acquired from UAVs or ground-based moving cameras. • Input from Task T4.3 will be used for defect identification to apply multiresolution capabilities in the region surrounding detected anomalies

Input Needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-resolution video or sequential high-resolution images. Input from Task T4.3
Verification Method	Quality metrics against users' perception, visual fidelity against ground truth, rendering quality metrics, projection errors
Comments	<p>The tool is highly dependent on the data capture. The entire target area must be thoroughly covered from multiple viewpoints to ensure accurate reconstruction. In the case of ground-based moving capture, the camera should remain as stable as possible while in motion. Extracted images should have significant overlap (ideally 70%).</p> <p>The output will be visualized according to the method that will be used. Possible options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local browser link for interactive viewing Export of 3D Gaussians to .ply file for external tools Method's integrated SIBR viewer
ID	TR-FUN-4.5-2
Name (Optional)	3D Reconstruction of Car Accident
Description	The tool transforms 2D visual data captured by UAVs at potential car accidents scenes into 3D replications, enhancing safety, enabling remote inspections, and providing valuable incident monitoring.
Category	Functional, Design
Related Tasks	T4.5 AI-driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring
Related Tool	3D-Smart Tool
Related Use Cases	UC 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain
MoSCoW Scale	should-have
Dependencies	High quality visual data acquired from UAVs or ground-based moving cameras.
Input Needed	High-resolution video or sequential high-resolution images.
Verification Method	Quality metrics against users' perception, visual fidelity against ground truth, rendering quality metrics, projection errors
Comments	The tool is highly dependent on the data capture. The entire target area must be thoroughly covered from multiple viewpoints to ensure accurate reconstruction. In the case of ground-based

	<p>moving capture, the camera should remain as stable as possible while in motion. Extracted images should have significant overlap (ideally 70%).</p> <p>The output will be visualized according to the method that will be used. Possible options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local browser link for interactive viewing Export of 3D Gaussians to .ply file for external tools Method's integrated SIBR viewer
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3.1.3 Requirements related to WP5

ID	TR-FUN-5.1-1
Name (Optional)	Data integration tool
Description	The systems must take account multi-source data from iDriving monitored network. Data must be adapted and process for continuous learning of KPI defined in SCC
Category	Design, interoperability
Related Tasks	Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning
Related Tool	Dynamic monitoring tool
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Safety Criteria Catalogue
Input Needed	Data from UCs relative to KPI define in SCC (data frequency, quality, or minima)
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.1-2
Name (Optional)	KPI computation and storage
Description	The system must compute KPI and learn indicators characteristics based on infrastructure and historical measurements. KPI are defined inside a SCC python database. The results are stored for evaluation, learning and visualisation.
Category	Functional

Related Tasks	Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning
Related Tool	Dynamic monitoring tool
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Safety Criteria Catalogue
Input Needed	Historical data from monitored areas
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.1-3
Name (Optional)	KPI monitoring dashboard
Description	The system shall provide a dashboard for visualizing KPI time series, supporting multiple visualization formats such as maps, heatmaps, and graphs.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning
Related Tool	Dynamic monitoring tool
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	Internet connection (API)
Input Needed	KPI data
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.1-4
Name (Optional)	KPI Continuous learning
Description	The system shall support forecasting and evaluation of KPIs based on incoming data streams.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Through Continuous Learning
Related Tool	Dynamic monitoring tool

Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	
Input Needed	KPI data, Traffic data
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.3-1
Name (Optional)	Data integration to digital twins
Description	The systems must take account multi-source data from iDriving monitored network. Data must be adapted and process to send to digital twin and store to perform offline calibration of digital twin simulation tools
Category	Functional, interoperability
Related Tasks	Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems
Related Tool	SUMO/CARLA
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	Traffic Data from UCs Data/events from ground camera or UAVs Weather data for UC2.2
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.3-2
Name (Optional)	Digital twin calibration
Description	The system shall build a digital twin of road networks in monitored areas to simulate road user behaviour based on real data. The resulting models shall be stored and made available for reuse within the iDriving project.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems

Related Tool	SUMO/CARLA, T3.2
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	Traffic Data from UCs
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.3-3
Name (Optional)	Multi road user simulation
Description	The system shall use a simulation-based digital twin to perform traffic prediction based on real-time and historical data. It shall generate user trajectories under various conditions and configurations.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems
Related Tool	SUMO
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	Traffic data, SUMO calibrated models
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.3-4
Name (Optional)	Intersection safety simulation
Description	The system shall perform a 3D simulation of critical area of the network (e.g. intersections) In order to evaluate risk for road-users.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems
Related Tool	CARLA

Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	Traffic data, SUMO calibrated models
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.3-5
Name (Optional)	Safety analysis and communication system
Description	From simulation data, provide alerts and safety measures for targeted network for iDriving prototype. Alerts are stored to perform safety assessment and tool evaluation.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems
Related Tool	SUMO/CARLA
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	must-have
Dependencies	-
Input Needed	Traffic data, SUMO calibrated models
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.4-1
Name (Optional)	Infrastructure Segment Risk Calculation
Description	The system shall calculate the dynamic risk for each infrastructure segment using both historical and real-time data, applying an FMEA-based risk assessment methodology. The risk calculation must consider road characteristics, traffic flow, and structural vulnerability information. This risk evaluation enables simulation of what-if scenarios and supports both the definition of maintenance needs and the planning of optimal maintenance interventions.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T5.4

Related Tool	Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool
Related Use Cases	UC2.1_4 (Karlovac), UC2.1_5
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Requires input from condition monitoring tools (detected structural vulnerabilities), traffic models and road characteristic data. Data integration with Tool 1.2 (Logistics Planning Tool)
Input Needed	Real-time road characteristics, traffic flow data, vulnerability data and scenario simulation results (optionally including damage information)
Verification Method	Validation of calculated risk metrics against expert assessments or field data; Functional tests verifying real-time risk updates when input conditions (e.g., traffic or vulnerability levels) change; Review of maintenance recommendations and plans generated based on risk indicators
Comments	This requirement is a key enabler for proactive maintenance strategies based on Digital Twin architecture. It ensures risk calculations are dynamically adapted to evolving road and traffic conditions and provides essential input to logistics and maintenance planning tools.
ID	TR-FUN-5.4-2
Name (Optional)	Dynamic calculation of Health Index / Road Condition Index (RCI)
Description	The system must dynamically compute Health Index or Road Condition Index values based on real-time (from condition monitoring and detecting road defects) and forecasted data, weather, and traffic.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T5.4
Related Tool	Health and Logistic Management Tool
Related Use Cases	UC2.1_4 (Karlovac)
MoSCoW Scale	Must Have
Dependencies	Integration with sensor-based data acquisition systems—primarily imaging devices—for road surface inspection; execution of computer vision algorithms to detect and classify road surface defects; and incorporation of weather and traffic forecasting pipelines to enable dynamic health index computation

Input Needed	Real-time or near real-time monitoring and processing of road condition data to estimate the infrastructure's health status, complemented by meteorological and traffic data to enhance the statistical accuracy of the health index estimation.
Verification Method	Comparison against actual condition measurements in pilot scenarios or simulated outcomes from Digital Twins model
Comments	Critical for enabling proactive and cost-effective maintenance. Enables downstream planning and risk analysis via connected tools (Module 1.1 and Module 1.3)
ID	TR-FUN-5.4-3
Name (Optional)	Maintenance Scheduling and Optimization
Description	The system must generate short- and long-term maintenance plans based on the dynamic risk, health indicators, traffic flow forecasts, weather conditions, and available resources. It must balance risk reduction, maintenance costs, and resource optimization by applying metaheuristic optimization algorithms and predefined operational constraints.
Category	Functional
Related Tasks	T5.4
Related Tool	Maintenance Scheduling Tool
Related Use Cases	UC2.1_4 (Karlovac), UC2.1_5
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Requires input from the Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool (Module 1.1) and Health and Logistics Management Tool (Module 1.2); Requires access to operational maintenance plans and constraints databases; Depends on real-time updates for traffic and weather forecasts.
Input Needed	Risk metrics, health indicators (RCI/Health Index), traffic forecasts, weather forecasts, predefined maintenance plans, available resource information
Verification Method	Validation through simulation of generated maintenance plans against expected optimization goals (cost vs risk trade-offs); Review of short-term and long-term plans to verify correct prioritization and resource assignment; Testing of exporting functionality (CSV/JSON formats).
Comments	Critical to ensure that maintenance interventions are not only risk-driven but also optimized for costs and operational feasibility. The tool must allow dynamic re-scheduling in case of updated risks or unexpected traffic/weather events. It is a key output component for

	supporting road managers in real-time and strategic decision-making.
ID	TR-FUN-5.5-1
Name (Optional)	Interface for Digital-Twin based control centre
Description	The system shall provide a user interface for the Digital Twin-based Control Center, compatible with both desktop applications and XR devices.
Category	Functional, Design, interoperability, security, regulatory/compliance
Related Tasks	T5.5 Digital Twin-Based Control Center with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness
Related Tool	Digital-Twin based control centre
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Interface depends on the device performance Data received from the other components (centralized at server level)
Input Needed	- User requirements list
Verification Method	Usability testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.5-2
Name (Optional)	Alerting and communication service
Description	The system shall include a dedicated service for bidirectional communication with the main server, handling the sending and receiving of messages, including alerts and notifications.
Category	Functional, Performance, interoperability, security, regulatory/compliance
Related Tasks	T5.5 Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness
Related Tool	Digital-Twin based control centre
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Internet Connection, External services (e.g. weather information)

Input Needed	Data schema definitions of the messages
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-
ID	TR-FUN-5.5-3
Name (Optional)	Dashboard for road operators
Description	The system shall provide a dashboard for road operators which will display statistics, logs, heatmaps, etc.
Category	Functional, Performance, interoperability, security
Related Tasks	T5.5 Digital Twin-Based Control Center with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness
Related Tool	Digital-Twin based control centre
Related Use Cases	UC1.1, UC1.2, UC2.1, UC2.2, UC3.1, UC3.2
MoSCoW Scale	Must-have
Dependencies	Internet Connection, External services (e.g. weather information)
Input Needed	Data schema definitions of the messages
Verification Method	Integration testing, functional testing
Comments	-

4 Technical & user requirements Mappings

This section presents the bidirectional mapping between the technical requirements specified in the current deliverable and the user requirements established in Deliverable D2.2. The purpose of this mapping is to ensure traceability, demonstrate coverage of user needs by technical solutions, and support ongoing alignment between system design and stakeholder expectations.

To provide full visibility, two complementary tables are included:

- **Table 77** lists, for each technical requirement, the corresponding user requirements it addresses.
- **Table 88** presents the inverse mapping, showing for each user requirement the technical requirement(s) that contribute to its fulfilment.

Both tables serve to highlight the many-to-many relationships inherent in the system specification process, where a single technical requirement may address multiple user needs, and conversely, each user requirement may be covered by more than one technical solution.

Note that the mappings are subject to refinement as both technical and user requirements evolve throughout the project lifecycle.

Table 7 – Technical requirement to user requirement mapping

Technical requirement	Work packages	User requirement(s)
TR-NFUN-GEN-9	ALL	UR_UC1.1_9, UR_UC1.2_10, UR_UC3.1_26
TR-FUN-3.2-1	WP3	UR_UC1.1_4, UR_UC1.1_5, UR_UC1.1_16, UR_UC2.2_10, UR_UC2.2_11, UR_UC2.2_15, UR_UC2.2_16, UR_UC3.2_1, UR_UC3.2_5, UR_UC3.2_6
TR-FUN-3.2-2	WP3	UR_UC2.1_8
TR-FUN-3.3-1	WP3	UR_UC1.1_6, UR_UC1.1_7, UR_UC1.1_8, UR_UC1.1_20, UR_UC1.2_17, UR_UC1.2_18, UR_UC1.2_19, UR_UC1.2_20, UR_UC1.2_21, UR_UC1.2_22, UR_UC1.2_23, UR_UC1.2_24, UR_UC1.2_25, UR_UC1.2_26, UR_UC1.2_27, UR_UC1.2_28, UR_UC2.2_6, UR_UC2.2_7, UR_UC2.2_8, UR_UC2.2_9, UR_UC2.2_13, UR_UC3.1_7, UR_UC3.1_8, UR_UC3.1_14, UR_UC3.1_18, UR_UC3.1_27, UR_UC3.2_1, UR_UC3.2_3, UR_UC3.2_4, UR_UC3.2_5, UR_UC3.2_12
TR-FUN-3.3-2	WP3	UR_UC1.1_8, UR_UC1.1_20, UR_UC1.1_25, UR_UC1.1_26, UR_UC1.2_14, UR_UC1.2_17, UR_UC1.2_18, UR_UC1.2_19, UR_UC1.2_20, UR_UC1.2_21, UR_UC1.2_22, UR_UC1.2_23,

		UR_UC1.2_24, UR_UC1.2_25, UR_UC1.2_26, UR_UC1.2_27, UR_UC1.2_28, UR_UC1.2_29, UR_UC1.2_30, UR_UC1.2_31, UR_UC1.2_32, UR_UC2.2_1, UR_UC2.2_2, UR_UC2.2_3, UR_UC2.2_4, UR_UC2.2_5, UR_UC2.2_12, UR_UC2.2_14, UR_UC3.1_6, UR_UC3.1_7, UR_UC3.1_16, UR_UC3.1_18, UR_UC3.1_23, UR_UC3.2_1, UR_UC3.2_2, UR_UC3.2_3, UR_UC3.2_6, UR_UC3.2_12
TR-FUN-3.5-1	WP3	UCR1.2_1, UCR1.2_2, UCR1.2_3, UCR1.2_4, UCR1.2_7, UCR1.2_9, UCR2.1_12, UCR2.1_13, UCR2.1_14, UCR2.2_33, UCR2.2_34, UCR2.2_35, UCR2.2_36, UCR3.2_9, UCR3.2_12
TR-FUN-3.5-2	WP3	UCR1.2_1, UCR1.2_2, UCR1.2_3, UCR1.2_4, UCR1.2_7, UCR1.2_9, UCR2.1_12, UCR2.1_13, UCR2.1_14, UCR2.2_33, UCR2.2_34, UCR2.2_35, UCR2.2_36, UCR3.2_9, UCR3.2_12
TR-FUN-3.5-3	WP3	UCR1.2_1, UCR1.2_2, UCR1.2_3, UCR1.2_4, UCR1.2_7, UCR1.2_9, UCR2.1_12, UCR2.1_13, UCR2.1_14, UCR2.2_33, UCR2.2_34, UCR2.2_35, UCR2.2_36, UCR3.2_9, UCR3.2_12
TR-NFUN-3.5-4	WP3	UCR1.2_1, UCR1.2_2, UCR1.2_3, UCR1.2_4, UCR1.2_7, UCR1.2_9, UCR2.1_12, UCR2.1_13, UCR2.1_14, UCR2.2_33, UCR2.2_34, UCR2.2_35, UCR2.2_36, UCR3.2_9, UCR3.2_12
TR-FUN-3.4.2	WP3	UR_UC1.2_2, UR_UC1.2_4, UR_UC1.2_5, UR_UC1.2_7, UR_UC1.2_13, UR_UC1.2_14, UR_UC1.2_15, UR_UC1.2_16
TR-NFUN-3.4.4	WP3	UR_UC1.1_1, UR_UC1.2_14, UR_UC1.2_23, UR_UC1.2_24, UR_UC1.2_25, UR_UC1.2_26, UR_UC3.1_7, UR_UC3.1_23
TR-NFUN-3.4.5	WP3	UR_UC1.1_9, UR_UC1.2_10
TR-FUN-4.1-1	WP4	UR_UC1.1_13
TR-FUN-4.1-2	WP4	UR_UC1.1_11, UR_UC1.2_1, UR_UC1.2_5, UR_UC1.2_8, UR_UC1.2_25
TR-FUN-4.1-3	WP4	UR_UC1.1_12
TR-FUN-4.1-4	WP4	UR_UC1.1_25, UR_UC1.2_13
TR-FUN-4.1-5	WP4	UR_UC1.1_3, UR_UC1.2_13, UR_UC1.2_15
TR-FUN-4.1-6	WP4	UR_UC1.2_7, UR_UC1.2_19, UR_UC1.2_24, UR_UC1.2_31
TR-FUN-4.1-7	WP4	UR_UC1.2_21, UR_UC2.2_33, UR_UC2.2_34, UR_UC2.2_35
TR-FUN-4.1-8	WP4	UR_UC3.2_7, UR_UC3.2_8, UR_UC3.2_12
TR-FUN-4.2-1	WP4	UR_UC1.1_10, UR_UC1.2_1, UR_UC1.2_8
TR-FUN-4.2-2	WP4	UR_UC1.1_14, UR_UC1.2_4, UR_UC1.2_22, UR_UC1.2_28, UR_UC1.2_30, UR_UC2.1_12, UR_UC3.1_3

TR-FUN-4.2-3	WP4	UR_UC1.2_7, UR_UC1.2_24, UR_UC1.2_31, UR_UC2.1_13
TR-FUN-4.2-4	WP4	UR_UC1.1_17, UR_UC1.2_2, UR_UC1.2_13, UR_UC1.2_15, UR_UC1.2_16, UR_UC1.2_32, UR_UC3.1_1, UR_UC3.1_2, UR_UC3.1_3, UR_UC3.2_8
TR-FUN-4.3-1	WP4	UR_UC2.1_1, UR_UC2.1_2
TR-FUN-4.3-2	WP4	UR_UC2.1_1, UR_UC2.1_2
TR-FUN-4.4-1	WP4	UR_UC1.2_11, UR_UC2.2_27, UR_UC2.2_28, UR_UC2.2_29, UR_UC2.2_30, UR_UC2.2_31, UR_UC2.2_32
TR-FUN-4.4-5	WP4	UR_UC2.2_27, UR_UC2.2_28, UR_UC2.2_29, UR_UC2.2_30, UR_UC2.2_31, UR_UC2.2_32
TR-FUN-4.5	WP4	UR_UC2.1_19, UR_UC3.2_10
TR-FUN-5.1-2	WP5	UR_UC1.1_19, UR_UC1.2_13, UR_UC1.2_15, UR_UC3.1_22, UR_UC3.2_11
TR-FUN-5.1-3	WP5	UR_UC1.1_23, UR_UC2.1_2, UR_UC3.1_21, UR_UC1.2_12, UR_UC3.1_22, UR_UC3.2_11, UR_UC1.2_16, UR_UC1.2_13
TR-FUN-5.1-4	WP5	UR_UC1.1_19, UR_UC1.2_13, UR_UC1.2_15, UR_UC1.2_16, UR_UC3.2_11
TR-FUN-5.3-3	WP5	UR_UC1.2_7, UR_UC1.2_1, UR_UC1.2_8
TR-FUN-5.3-4	WP5	UR_UC1.1_21, UR_UC1.2_13
TR-FUN-5.3-5	WP5	UR_UC1.1_3, UR_UC1.1_20, UR_UC1.1_22, UR_UC1.1_24, UR_UC1.2_14, UR_UC1.2_17, UR_UC1.2_18, UR_UC1.2_19, UR_UC1.2_20, UR_UC1.2_21, UR_UC1.2_22, UR_UC1.2_23, UR_UC1.2_24, UR_UC1.2_25, UR_UC1.2_26, UR_UC1.2_27, UR_UC1.2_28, UR_UC1.2_29, UR_UC1.2_30, UR_UC1.2_31, UR_UC1.2_32, UR_UC3.1_13, UR_UC3.1_16, UR_UC3.1_28,
TR-FUN-5.4-1	WP5	UR_UC2.1_4, UR_UC2.1_1, UR_UC2.1_8
TR-FUN-5.4-3	WP5	UR_UC2.1_5
TR-FUN-5.5-1	WP5	UR_UC1.1_8, UR_UC1.1_20, UR_UC1.2_12, UR_UC2.1_7, UR_UC2.1_15, UR_UC2.2_18, UR_UC2.2_19, UR_UC3.1_21
TR-FUN-5.5-2	WP5	UR_UC1.2_14, UR_UC1.2_25, UR_UC1.2_26, UR_UC1.2_27, UR_UC1.2_28, UR_UC1.2_29, UR_UC1.2_30, UR_UC1.2_31, UR_UC1.2_32, UR_UC2.1_9, UR_UC2.1_10, UR_UC2.1_11, UR_UC2.1_17, UR_UC3.1_7, UR_UC3.1_16, UR_UC3.1_23
TR-FUN-5.5-3	WP5	UR_UC1.1_8, UR_UC1.1_20, UR_UC1.2_12, UR_UC1.2_13, UR_UC1.2_15, UR_UC1.2_16, UR_UC2.1_3, UR_UC2.1_6, UR_UC2.2_17, UR_UC2.2_20, UR_UC2.2_23, UR_UC2.2_24, UR_UC2.2_25, UR_UC2.2_26, UR_UC3.1_21, UR_UC3.1_22

Table 8 - User requirement to technical requirement mapping

User Requirement	Technical Requirement(s)
UR_UC1.1_1	TR-NFUN-3.4.4
UR_UC1.1_3	TR-FUN-4.1-5, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.1_4	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC1.1_5	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC1.1_6	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC1.1_7	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC1.1_8	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.5-1, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC1.1_9	TR-NFUN-GEN-9, TR-NFUN-3.4.5
UR_UC1.1_10	TR-FUN-4.2-1
UR_UC1.1_11	TR-FUN-4.1-2
UR_UC1.1_12	TR-FUN-4.1-3
UR_UC1.1_13	TR-FUN-4.1-1
UR_UC1.1_14	TR-FUN-4.2-2
UR_UC1.1_16	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC1.1_17	TR-FUN-4.2-4
UR_UC1.1_19	TR-FUN-5.1-2, TR-FUN-5.1-4
UR_UC1.1_20	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5, TR-FUN-5.5-1, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC1.1_21	TR-FUN-5.3-4
UR_UC1.1_22	TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.1_23	TR-FUN-5.1-3
UR_UC1.1_24	TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.1_25	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.1-4
UR_UC1.2_1	TR-FUN-4.1-2, TR-FUN-4.2-1, TR-FUN-5.3-3
UR_UC1.2_2	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-4.2-4
UR_UC1.2_3	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4
UR_UC1.2_4	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-4.2-2

UR_UC1.2_5	TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-4.1-2
UR_UC1.2_7	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-4.1-6, TR-FUN-4.2-3, TR-FUN-5.3-3
UR_UC1.2_8	TR-FUN-4.1-2, TR-FUN-4.2-1, TR-FUN-5.3-3
UR_UC1.2_9	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4
UR_UC1.2_10	TR-NFUN-GEN-9, TR-NFUN-3.4.5
UR_UC1.2_11	TR-FUN-4.4-1
UR_UC1.2_12	TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-5.5-1, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC1.2_13	TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-4.1-4, TR-FUN-4.1-5, TR-FUN-4.2-4, TR-FUN-5.1-2, TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-5.1-4, TR-FUN-5.3-4, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC1.2_14	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-5.3-5, TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC1.2_15	TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-4.1-5, TR-FUN-4.2-4, TR-FUN-5.1-2, TR-FUN-5.1-4, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC1.2_16	TR-FUN-3.4.2, TR-FUN-4.2-4, TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-5.1-4
UR_UC1.2_17	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_18	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_19	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.1-6, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_20	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_21	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.1-7, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_22	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.2-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_23	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_24	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-FUN-4.1-6, TR-FUN-4.2-3, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_25	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-FUN-4.1-2, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_26	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_27	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_28	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.2-2, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_29	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_30	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.2-2, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5

UR_UC1.2_31	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.1-6, TR-FUN-4.2-3, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC1.2_32	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.2-4, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC2.1_1	TR-FUN-4.3-1, TR-FUN-4.3-2, TR-FUN-5.4-1
UR_UC2.1_2	TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-4.3-1, TR-FUN-4.3-2
UR_UC2.1_3	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.1_4	TR-FUN-5.4-1
UR_UC2.1_5	TR-FUN-5.4-3
UR_UC2.1_6	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.1_7	TR-FUN-5.5-1
UR_UC2.1_8	TR-FUN-3.2-2, TR-FUN-5.4-1
UR_UC2.1_9	TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC2.1_10	TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC2.1_11	TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC2.1_12	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-4.2-2
UR_UC2.1_13	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-4.2-3
UR_UC2.1_14	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4
UR_UC2.1_15	TR-FUN-5.5-1
UR_UC2.1_17	TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC2.1_19	TR-FUN-4.5
UR_UC2.2_1	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_2	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_3	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_4	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_5	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_6	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC2.2_7	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC2.2_8	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC2.2_9	TR-FUN-3.3-1

UR_UC2.2_10	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC2.2_11	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC2.2_12	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_13	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC2.2_14	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC2.2_15	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC2.2_16	TR-FUN-3.2-1
UR_UC2.2_17	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.2_18	TR-FUN-5.5-1
UR_UC2.2_19	TR-FUN-5.5-1
UR_UC2.2_20	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.2_23	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.2_24	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.2_25	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.2_26	TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC2.2_27	TR-FUN-4.4-1, TR-FUN-4.4-5
UR_UC2.2_28	TR-FUN-4.4-1, TR-FUN-4.4-5
UR_UC2.2_29	TR-FUN-4.4-1, TR-FUN-4.4-5
UR_UC2.2_30	TR-FUN-4.4-1, TR-FUN-4.4-5
UR_UC2.2_31	TR-FUN-4.4-1, TR-FUN-4.4-5
UR_UC2.2_32	TR-FUN-4.4-1, TR-FUN-4.4-5
UR_UC2.2_33	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-4.1-7
UR_UC2.2_34	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-4.1-7
UR_UC2.2_35	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4, TR-FUN-4.1-7
UR_UC2.2_36	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4
UR_UC3.1_1	TR-FUN-4.2-4
UR_UC3.1_2	TR-FUN-4.2-4
UR_UC3.1_3	TR-FUN-4.2-2, TR-FUN-4.2-4

UR_UC3.1_6	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC3.1_7	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC3.1_8	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC3.1_13	TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC3.1_14	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC3.1_16	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-5.3-5, TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC3.1_18	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC3.1_21	TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-5.5-1, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC3.1_22	TR-FUN-5.1-2, TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-5.5-3
UR_UC3.1_23	TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-FUN-5.5-2
UR_UC3.1_26	TR-NFUN-GEN-9
UR_UC3.1_27	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC3.1_28	TR-FUN-5.3-5
UR_UC3.2_1	TR-FUN-3.2-1, TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC3.2_2	TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC3.2_3	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC3.2_4	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC3.2_5	TR-FUN-3.2-1, TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC3.2_6	TR-FUN-3.2-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2
UR_UC3.2_7	TR-FUN-4.1-8
UR_UC3.2_8	TR-FUN-4.1-8, TR-FUN-4.2-4
UR_UC3.2_9	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4
UR_UC3.2_10	TR-FUN-4.5
UR_UC3.2_11	TR-FUN-5.1-2, TR-FUN-5.1-3, TR-FUN-5.1-4
UR_UC3.2_12	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2, TR-FUN-4.1-8
UR_UC3.2_13	TR-FUN-3.3-1
UR_UC3.2_14	TR-FUN-3.3-2

5 Overall Architecture & Components

5.1 Methodology for Defining the Architecture

The iDriving architecture adopts the [C4 Model](#), a widely recognized methodology for the visualization and communication of complex software systems. This approach enables clear, layered representations that address different stakeholder concerns, ranging from the overall business context to detailed technical designs.

The C4 Model, specifically selected for this deliverable, provides the following architectural perspectives:

- **Context View:** Illustrates the system as a “black box” in its environment, identifying all major external actors and their interactions with iDriving.
- **Container View:** Breaks down iDriving into its main technology containers (applications, databases, services), focusing on the responsibilities and integration points between them for each use case.
- **Component View:** (Detailed per-container) Provides a further breakdown of how key containers are internally structured and how their sub-components collaborate to realize functional requirements.
- **Code View:** (Omitted from this deliverable) Reserved for implementation-level details.

This layered approach ensures all audiences—technical, managerial, and operational—can clearly understand the system at the right level of abstraction for their needs. Furthermore, the model’s modularity allows us to articulate both common patterns across use cases and bespoke design elements that address unique local challenges.

5.2 iDriving Context View

The **Context View** (see Figure 2) presents a high-level overview of the iDriving ecosystem, visualizing its position within the wider operational and stakeholder landscape. This diagram identifies the main categories of external actors—**Traffic Authorities / Road Operators, UAV Operators / Maintenance Teams**, and **Road Users**—and delineates their primary data exchanges with the iDriving system.

Purpose:

The Context View establishes the project’s system boundaries, clarifies roles and responsibilities, and sets the stage for understanding subsequent architectural details. It ensures that all project stakeholders—from technical teams to management and end users—share a mutual understanding of who interacts with iDriving and what the essential information flows are.

Figure 2 - iDriving Context View

5.3 iDriving Containers View

The **Container View** diagrams provide a focused breakdown of the iDriving system into its major functional and technological building blocks (“containers”). These diagrams capture the core architecture of iDriving, presenting a layered representation that organizes system components according to their roles in the overall workflow:

- **Data Acquisition:** Edge devices, sensors, UAVs, and other sources responsible for gathering raw data from the field.
- **Detection & Prediction:** AI/ML tools and visual analytics modules that transform raw data into actionable insights and early warnings.
- **Core Back-End & Optimization:** Centralized services, orchestration engines, and simulation tools, which process, store, and optimize system outputs.
- **User-Facing & Control:** Applications, dashboards, and control centres that deliver insights and instructions to end users and operators.

Colour Coding and Layering:

Each container in the diagram is color-coded to reflect its alignment with specific Tasks, ensuring immediate visual clarity regarding component ownership and functional grouping. Layered structuring (vertical separation) emphasizes the flow of data and control from acquisition through to actionable outcomes.

Purpose:

The Containers View enables all stakeholders to grasp briefly and immediately, which software and hardware modules are active in a given use case, how data moves between them, and how the overall system achieves its functional and non-functional requirements. This approach facilitates traceability from user needs to technical solutions, supports impact analysis for changes, and provides a strong basis for further detailed design in the Components' View.

5.3.1 Containers View – Consolidated

This section provides a **unified Container View diagram** that aggregates the common architectural elements across all use cases. It highlights the shared infrastructure, core backend services, and cross-cutting components (e.g., Dataspace Connector, Kafka broker) that underpin the iDriving ecosystem. This consolidated view supports system-wide integration and reuse.

Legend

Task 3.1
Task 3.2
Task 3.3
Task 3.4
Task 3.5
Task 4.1
Task 4.2
Task 4.3
Task 4.4
Task 4.5
Task 5.1
Task 5.2
Task 5.3
Task 5.4
Task 5.5

Figure 4 - Containers View Colour Legend

5.3.2 Containers View Per Use Case

While the consolidated view outlines an overall logical view of the system, each pilot deployment has its own architectural nuances. The following sub-sections present **use-case-specific Container View diagrams**, showcasing localized deployment patterns, data flows, and components tailored to the particular context and objectives of each site.

5.3.2.1 Use case 1.1 Graz, Austria

Container View diagram for UC 1.1 Graz is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Use Case 1.1 Containers View

5.3.2.2 Use Case 1.2 Nevers, France

Container View diagram for UC 1.2 Nevers is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - Use Case 1.2 Containers View

5.3.2.3 Use Case 2.1 Karlovac, Croatia

Container View diagram for UC 2.1 Karlovac is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Use Case 2.1 Containers View

5.3.2.4 Use case 2.2 Thessaloniki, Greece

Container View diagram for UC 2.2 Thessaloniki is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Use Case 2.2 Containers View

5.3.2.5 Use case 3.1 Alba Iulia, Romania

Container View diagram for UC 3.1 Alba Iulia is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Use Case 3.1 Containers View

5.3.2.6 Use case 3.2 Bizkaia, Spain

Container View diagram for UC 3.2 Bizkaia is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Use Case 3.2 Containers View

5.4 iDriving Components Views & Specifications

This section presents detailed component-level architecture for each key element of the iDriving system. Each diagram offers a deeper perspective on the internal structure and functional composition of a component identified in the previous Container Views. The goal is to illustrate how each “container” is organized into sub-components, how responsibilities are allocated internally, and how interfaces are defined both within the component and with other system elements.

For every component, the accompanying specification table summarizes its purpose, deployment considerations, expected technology readiness level, key dependencies, and links to the relevant technical requirements. This structure ensures that the documentation is comprehensive and actionable for all stakeholders involved in the design, implementation, and integration of the system.

By aligning component views with the broader architectural framework, this section supports traceability from high-level requirements and container interactions down to the level of internal modules and integration points, enabling consistent development and effective collaboration across all partners.

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In Tables 9 to 38 each core component of the iDriving system is detailed with its architectural diagram, internal sub-components, and specifications that summarize its purpose, deployment approach, expected technology readiness level, key dependencies, involved partners, and links to relevant technical requirements.

Table 9 - Tekniker Dataspace Connector - Architectural Design and Description

Tekniker Dataspace Connector: Network Infrastructure Development and Asset Intercommunication	
Description	A modular solution that allows organizations to establish a single point of entry for accessing and exchanging data within a data space. It ensures interoperability in data sharing, fosters trust among participants, and guarantees data sovereignty throughout its entire lifecycle.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	
Expected TRL	TRL6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Docker

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HTTP
Deployment Premises	Containerized deployment using Docker
Involved Partners	TEKNIKER
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-3.1-1, TR-FUN-3.1-2

Table 10 - Route Guidance tool Architectural Design and Description

Route Guidance Tool: Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows	
Description	The system receives information from different sources (cameras, UAVs, magnetic loop detectors etc.). The feed is already processed and transformed to ready-to-use information, such as traffic flow or density or space-mean speed per road (link), incident type and location. The origin-destination per vehicle type is considered known for the network being analysed. An affected area is identified and all trips traversing this area will receive rerouting guidance. New routes are calculated for every affected trip considering the vehicle type, which avoid the affected area and increase safety and efficiency of the trips. The suggested alternative paths are communicated to the respective vehicles.

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Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)

Expected TRL	TRL
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the component: <ul style="list-style-type: none">SUMO traffic simulation software
Deployment Premises	The testing of the various scenarios defined will be done in simulated environment and/or in real-time implementation. The route guidance tool will be an add-on module for SUMO traffic simulator. The system will be tested virtually on servers within the partners' premises.
Involved Partners	MBL; TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-3.2-1

Table 11 - Signal Control Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Signal Control Tool: Safety-Optimized Traffic Management Using Intelligent Algorithms for Diverse Vehicle Flows	
Description	<p>The system receives information from different sources (cameras, induction loop detectors, magnetometer sensors etc.). The signal control tool provides dynamic adjustment of traffic light timings for an identified intersection(s) based on the actual traffic information coming from the neighbouring links of the intersection. At each signal cycle, measurements or estimates of queue lengths or accumulated vehicles are feeding the control strategy, whose main goal is to improve efficiency of the trips served by the controlled intersection(s). The optimal signal timings are computed in real-time and broadcasted to the traffic lights.</p>

Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)

Expected TRL

TRL

Technologies

The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the Signal Control Component:

- SUMO traffic simulation software

Deployment Premises	The testing of the various scenarios defined will be done in a simulated environment and/or in real-time implementation. The signal control tool will be an add-on module for the SUMO traffic simulator. The system will be tested virtually on servers within the partners' premises.
Involved Partners	MBL; TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-3.2-2

Table 12 - Mobile Application – Architectural Design and Description

Mobile Application: Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings	
Description	A user-centric software system that serves both drivers and non-driving road users. It connects directly to user’s mobile device (Android system) and the Digital Twin to fetch real-time data on road conditions, traffic, and other potential hazards
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<pre> graph LR User((iDriving User [Person] Road users.)) --> Auth[Authentication module [Service: e.g. Unity] Supports the authentication process of the user.] Auth --> UI[UI module [Service: e.g. Unity] Display the output of the related services, relevant messages for the user.] Comm[Communication module [Service: e.g. Unity] Enables the communication with the backend.] --> UI Comm --> Messages[Messages module [Service: e.g. Unity] Processes the information received from the backend and prepares it for the frontend.] Messages --> UI subgraph Frontend [Frontend [Mobile Application]] Auth UI Comm Messages end Backend[Backend [Server: e.g. Kafka] Supports the authentication process, messaging system.] Frontend <--> rest API Backend </pre> <p>The diagram illustrates the architectural design of the Mobile Application. It features an iDriving User (Person) who interacts with the Frontend (Mobile Application). The Frontend is composed of four modules: Authentication module (Service: e.g. Unity), UI module (Service: e.g. Unity), Communication module (Service: e.g. Unity), and Messages module (Service: e.g. Unity). The Authentication module supports the authentication process of the user. The UI module displays the output of related services and relevant messages for the user. The Communication module enables communication with the backend. The Messages module processes information received from the backend and prepares it for the frontend. The Frontend interacts with the Backend (Server: e.g. Kafka) via a rest API. The Backend supports the authentication process and messaging system.</p>

Expected TRL	TRL6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unity • C# • REST API • Photoshop • Blender 3D
Deployment Premises	Android based mobile device with WiFi connection
Involved Partners	TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2

Table 13 - In-Vehicle Application – Architectural Design and Description

In-Vehicle Application: Mobile and in-vehicle applications for early warnings	
Description	A user-centric software system that serves drivers. It connects directly to the vehicle’s built in infotainment system (Android system) and the Digital Twin to fetch real-time data on road conditions, traffic, and other potential hazards

Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)

Expected TRL TRL6

Technologies The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:

- Unity
- C#
- REST API

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Photoshop• Blender 3D
Deployment Premises	In-vehicle Android system with WiFi connection
Involved Partners	TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-3.3-1, TR-FUN-3.3-2

Table 14 - Aerial Surveillance UAV System – Architectural Design and Description

Aerial Surveillance UAV system: Aerial Surveillance in Incident Management and Maintenance Tasks	
Description	<p>A UAV system will be delivered, equipped with the ability to host different sensors and cameras (i.e. high-resolution camera, thermal etc.) in order to ensure precise, efficient, effective data collection from the areas of interest on demand and/or near real time and address the iDriving specific needs in trials.</p> <p>The UAV will be able to perform manual or autonomous flights by preparing a flight plan prior to the mission.</p> <p>For the pilot use cases and in the case of the need to execute the AI Algorithms in near real-time, the following two approaches are available:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A NVIDIA AI-oriented computer will be available for mounting on the UAV where the payloads will interact with the onboard computer to achieve the objectives of each specific mission according to PUC requirements. 2. Transfer the video stream in real time in the ground station computer where the AI algorithms will be installed, executed, and then transfer the required data to any cloud/server needed.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. At the top is the GNSS Receiver, which is bidirectionally connected to the PX4 AutoPilot. The On-board Computer is connected to the PX4 AutoPilot and also receives input from a Sensors block containing RGB and Thermal cameras. The PX4 AutoPilot is connected to a Telemetry block via the MAVLink Protocol and to a Remote Control Receiver block via 868 MHz. The Telemetry block is connected to a ground station laptop via the MAVLink Protocol and 433 MHz. The Remote Control Receiver is connected to a ground station RC controller via 868 MHz. The ground station laptop is connected to the On-board Computer via 4G/5G and Wi-Fi. The RC controller is labeled 'Real-time video streaming'.</p>

Expected TRL	Current TRL: 4 Expected TRL: 6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the Mission UAV: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UAV Hardware • Onboard or Ground Processors • AI Algorithms
Deployment Premises	Depends on the Use Case.
Involved Partners	TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-NFUN-3.4.1, TR-NFUN-3.4.2, TR-NFUN-3.4.3, TR-NFUN-3.4.4, TR-NFUN-3.4.5

Table 15 - Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage – Architectural Design and Description

Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage: Dynamic Resource Allocation for Optimized Safety Surveillance	
Description	<p>This task will provide an AI-based service for autonomous designing of missions for a single or a swarm of UAV(s) to cover (map + monitor) large areas. This service will be triggered by the area to be covered (e.g. a polygon in WGS84 coordinates), that might include obstacles/no-fly-zones, and the number of UAVs that are operational and ready to participate in the mission. This service will carefully design the paths for all the UAVs to: i) ensure complete area coverage, ii) maximize UAV utilization, iii) avoid unwanted overlaps, iv) minimize turns that increase mission duration and energy consumption, and v) deliver the required visual output in minimal time. Additionally, in case of multiple UAVs, the service will not provide “blindly” equal paths, but it will incorporate each UAV’s characteristics (e.g. maximum operation time, remaining battery, etc.) to produce paths tailored to their operational capabilities. Finally, the paths will be designed in such a way to be ready for execution not only once, in a case where just a “snapshot” of the operational area is needed, but also in a continuous manner, in a form of patrolling the whole area, capable of monitoring the evolution of underlying, dynamically evolving phenomena. To support this functionality, an end-to-end platform will be developed. This platform will allow users to define mission parameters, upload or draw areas of interest, monitor UAV assignments, visualize generated paths, and initiate missions. It will serve as the main interface between the user and the planning service, ensuring usability, flexibility, and seamless integration with other components of the system.</p>

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>Current TRL: 4 Expected TRL: 6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Backend <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python for implementing the coverage path planning algorithm • GIS libraries (e.g., GeoPandas, Shapely) for handling geospatial data in WGS84 format ➤ Frontend <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web-based interface technologies (React, NextJS, TailwindCSS, Typescript, React Query, Zustand) for visualizing input areas and planned paths <p>Output mission plans (e.g., waypoint lists) will follow standardized formats such as JSON, enabling compatibility with existing UAV autopilot systems</p>
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>At CERTH's premises</p>

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Involved Partners	UNI.EIFFEL, TUC, MBL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-3.5-1, TR-FUN-3.5-2, TR-FUN-3.5-3, TR-NFUN-3.5-4

Table 16 - Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	This tool uses advanced embedded object detection algorithms, such as those deployed on NVIDIA's Jetson platform, to analyse video feeds from road cameras. It identifies whether drivers are wearing seat belts or using a mobile phone while driving. By automatically flagging these violations, it helps monitor compliance with traffic regulations.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<pre> graph TD subgraph ODE [ODE - Running on embedded device] AerialUAV[Aerial UAV System [UAV camera input] Task 3.4] StreetCamera[Street Camera Input [Data Source] Input from road cameras] StreamIngestion[Stream Ingestion Module [Component: Stream Ingestion] Captures real-time video feed] DetectionModel[SeatBelt & Mobile Detection Model [Component: ML object detection] Model detects driver violations: Seat belts, Mobile] EventProcessor[Event Processor [Component:] -Formats the results (e.g., timestamp, location, violation type) -Prepares the data for the UI] AerialUAV --> StreamIngestion StreetCamera --> StreamIngestion StreamIngestion --> DetectionModel DetectionModel --> EventProcessor end EventProcessor --> Kafka[KAFKA broker [Container: e.g. Apache Kafka] Message bus] Kafka --> JSONOutput[JSON Output [JSON File] Formats the results (e.g., timestamp, location, violation type)] Kafka --> UI[UI / Visualization [Container:] iDriving Platform] Kafka --> MobileApp[Mobile App [JSON metadata] Task 3.3] Kafka --> ClaireSITI[ClaireSITI [JSON metadata] Task 5.1] </pre>
Expected TRL	TRL 6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deep learning detection models
Deployment Premises	Embedded on edge device
Involved Partners	SIMAVI, TEKNIKER, UNI.EIFFEL, MBL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN- 4.1-1, TR-FUN-4.1-2, TR-FUN-4.1-3,

Table 17 - Count Cars Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Count cars Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	It is designed to count cars in the current frame
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	
Expected TRL	TRL 6

Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • Deep learning detection models
Deployment Premises	Embedded on edge device
Involved Partners	MBL, UNI.EIFFEL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.1-5

Table 18 - License Plate Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

License Plate Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	This tool runs on embedded devices and uses computer vision algorithms to automatically identify license plates from video footage once a traffic violation is detected. After recognizing offenses such as seat belt non-compliance or cell phone usage while driving, the tool accurately captures the license plate of the offending vehicle.

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<pre> graph TD subgraph ODE [ODE - Running on embedded device] A[Stream Ingestion Module [Component: Stream Ingestion] Captures real-time video feed] --> B[LP Detection Model [Component: ML object detection] Detect license plate of the offender] B --> C[Event Processor [Component:] Prepares the data for the UI] end C --> D[(KAFKA broker [Container: e.g. Apache Kafka] Message bus)] D --> E[UI / Visualization [Container:] iDriving Platform] </pre>
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL 6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • Deep learning detection models
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>The tool will run on an embedded device such as the NVIDIA Jetson</p>
<p>Involved Partners</p>	<p>SIMAVI, TEKNIKER, UNI.EIFFEL</p>
<p>Related Technical requirements</p>	<p>TR-FUN-4.1-4,</p>

Table 19 - Helmet Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Helmet Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	This tool leverages advanced computer vision algorithms to automatically detect helmet usage by motorcyclists or cyclists in real-time. It can run on embedded devices connected to road cameras or UAVs (drones), enabling effective monitoring of helmet compliance in various environments. By ensuring riders wear helmets, the tool promotes safety and supports traffic regulation enforcement.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	
Expected TRL	TRL 6
Technologies	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • Deep learning detection models

Deployment Premises	The tool will run on an embedded device such as the NVIDIA Jetson
Involved Partners	SIMAVI, TEKNIKER, UNI.EIFFEL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.1-3

Table 20 - Zebra Crossing Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Zebra Crossing Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	The system shall detect the presence of zebra crossing in video frames captured by roadside cameras or UAVs
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<pre> graph TD A[Street Camera Input [Data Source] Input from road cameras] --> B[Stream Ingestion Module [Component: Stream Ingestion] Captures real-time video feed] C[Aerial UAV System [UAV camera input] Task 3.4] --> B subgraph ODE [ODE [Running on embedded device]] B --> D[Zebra Crossing Detection Model [Component: ML object detection] Model detects driver violations: Zebra Crossings] D --> E[Event Processor [Component:] -Formats the results (e.g., timestamp, location, violation type) -Prepares the data for the UI] end E --> F[KAFKA broker [Container: e.g. Apache Kafka] Message bus] F --> G[TEKNIKER [User] Task 4.2] </pre>
Expected TRL	TRL 6

Technologies	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • Deep learning detection models
Deployment Premises	The tool will run on an embedded device such as the NVIDIA Jetson
Involved Partners	TEKNIKER
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.1-6

Table 21 - Fallen Tree and Rockslide Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Fallen tree and Rockslide Plate Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	This tool utilizes computer vision algorithms to monitor landscapes and roadways for fallen trees and rockslides using video feeds from UAVs (drones). It analyses aerial imagery to quickly identify and assess potential hazards, enabling prompt reporting and response.

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<p>The diagram illustrates the system architecture. It starts with a Drone Camera Input [Data Source] providing Input from UAV. This feeds into a Stream Ingestion Module [Component: Stream Ingestion] which Captures real-time video feed. The data then goes to a Disaster Detection Model [Component: ML object detection] which Model detects driver violations: Fallen Trees & Rock slides. This is followed by an Event Processor [Component:] which -Formats the results (e.g., timestamp, location, violation type) and -Prepares the data for the UI. These three components are part of the ODE [Running on embedded device]. The processed data is sent to a KAFKA broker [Container: e.g. Apache Kafka] acting as a Message bus. From the Kafka broker, data is distributed to: UI / Visualization [Container:] (iDriving Platform), JSON Output [JSON File] (Formats the results (e.g., timestamp, location, violation type)), CARLA [JSON metadata] (Task 5.3), and SUMO [JSON metadata] (Task 5.4).</p>
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL 6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • Deep learning detection models
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>The tool will run on an embedded device such as the NVIDIA Jetson</p>
<p>Involved Partners</p>	<p>MBL, UNI.EIFFEL, ACCELI</p>
<p>Related Technical requirements</p>	<p>TR-FUN- 4.1-7</p>

Table 22 - Crashed Vehicle Detection Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Crashed vehicle Detection Tool: Real-Time Edge Computing for Visual Monitoring	
Description	This tool employs computer vision algorithms to identify crashed vehicles in real-time using video feeds from CCTV cameras or UAVs (drones). It analyses the imagery to detect unusual stationary vehicles or collisions on the road, promptly alerting emergency services.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<pre> graph TD subgraph ODE [ODE - Running on embedded device] direction TB A[Street Camera Input [Data Source] Input from road cameras] --> B[Stream Ingestion Module [Component: Stream Ingestion] Captures real-time video feed] C[Drone Camera Input [Data Source] Input from UAV] --> B B --> D[Car Crash Detection Model [Component: ML object detection] Model detects driver violations: Crashed Cars] D --> E[Event Processor [Component:] -Formats the results (e.g., timestamp, location, violation type) -Prepares the data for the UI] end E --> F[(KAFKA broker [Container: e.g. Apache Kafka] Message bus)] F --> G[UI / Visualization [Container:] iDriving Platform] F --> H[Signal Control Tool [JSON metadata] Task 3.2] F --> I[CARLA [JSON metadata] Task 5.3] F --> J[SUMO [JSON metadata] Task 5.4] </pre>
Expected TRL	TRL 6
Technologies	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python • Deep learning detection models
Deployment Premises	The tool will run on an embedded device such as the NVIDIA Jetson
Involved Partners	ACCELI, UNI.EIFFEL, MBL, TEKNIKER

Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.1-8
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Table 23 - Red Light Violation Detector – Architectural Design and Description

Red light violation detector: AI-Powered Behavioural analysis of objects of interest	
Description	An intelligent vision-based module that monitors vehicle behaviour at intersections. It detects if a vehicle has crossed a virtual stop line during a red traffic light phase by combining real-time vehicle detection and tracking, traffic light data and rule-based violation detection logic. This component supports evidence generation for enforcement and real-time alerts for traffic management systems.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<p>Subcomponents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detector: Locates vehicles in each video frame. - Tracker: assigns unique IDs to each vehicle and maintains its trajectory - Violation Engine: verifies virtual line crossing, evaluates whether the crossing occurred during a red traffic light phase, and triggers an alert. - Exporter: saves evidence (image + timestamp + ID + traffic light status)
Expected TRL	TRL 5-6

Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the Component: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The software shall be implemented primarily in Python - SQLite, PostgreSQL, or MongoDB for export
Deployment Premises	On-premises service
Involved Partners	CERTH, TEKNIKER, SIMAVI, UNIV-EIFFEL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.2-1

Table 24 - Improper Lane Usage Detector – Architectural Design and Description

Improper line usage detector: AI-Powered Behavioural analysis of objects of interest	
Description	This module detects improper lane usage by vehicles in urban segments. The system analyses the trajectory of each vehicle in real-time to determine whether it deviates from its assigned lane or enters restricted zones. It uses object detection, tracking, and spatial reasoning to identify violations.

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<p>Subcomponents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detector: Locates vehicles in each vide frame. - Tracker: assigns unique IDs to each vehicle and maintains its trajectory - Violation Engine: validates vehicle trajectories based on the land zone. It compares the vehicle’s trajectory with the allowed lane zones. - Exporter: saves evidence (image + timestamp + ID + lane info)
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL 5-6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>On-premises</p>
<p>Involved Partners</p>	<p>CERTH, TEKNIKER, SIMAVI, UNIV-EIFFEL</p>
<p>Related Technical requirements</p>	<p>TR-FUN-4.2-2</p>

Table 25 - Zebra Crossing Violation Detector – Architectural Design and Description

Zebra crossing violation detector: AI-Powered Behavioural analysis of objects of interest

<p>Description</p>	<p>This component aims to detect when a pedestrian is walking or crossing outside the spatial boundaries of a zebra crossing by analysing video frames. It performs real-time pedestrian detection and tracking combined with zebra crossing segmentation using computer vision. By comparing the tracked pedestrian's position with the extracted geometric limits of the zebra crossing, the component can determine when a pedestrian is violating the designated crossing area.</p>
<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<p>The architecture integrates five core subcomponents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Video Stream Input: Ingests RTSP or recorded footage from fixed surveillance cameras. 2. Pedestrian Detection & Tracking: Detects and follows individuals across frames. 3. Zebra Crossing Segmentation: Identifies zebra crossing zones using computer vision techniques. 4. Violation Analyzer: Compares pedestrian positions with zebra masks using spatial logic (e.g., point-in-polygon) to detect improper crossings or unsafe behaviour. 5. Alert & Logging Module: Flags violations, generates alerts, and stores visual/log evidence for later review. <p>The system is designed for modular deployment.</p>
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL 5-6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>On premises</p>

Involved Partners	CERTH, TEKNIKER, SIMAVI, UNIV-EIFFEL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.2.3

Table 26 - Abrupt Movements Detector – Architectural Design and Description

Abrupt movements detector: AI-Powered Behavioural analysis of objects of interest	
Description	This component aims to identify anomalous driving events in vehicles characterized by sudden accelerations, braking, steering actions, or irregular trajectories. The system will analyse sensor data (accelerometer, gyroscope, and GPS) to detect behaviours that could indicate dangerous or erratic driving: exceeding speed limits, sudden acceleration, harsh braking, abrupt steering, irregular trajectories.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	</pre>
Expected TRL	TRL 5-6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Python (NumPy, SciPy, pandas, tslearn, statsmodels, scikit-learn...)
Deployment Premises	On premises
Involved Partners	TEKNIKER, AIM, SIMAVI

Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.2.4
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Table 27 - Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool: Visual analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements	
<p>Description</p>	<p>An advanced AI model will be developed to identify road defects, such as potholes and cracks. This system will analyse images or videos captured by various sources, including drones, dash cameras in vehicles, and fixed traffic surveillance cameras. The AI model will process this visual data to detect and annotate road defects accurately. Furthermore, the model will generate supplementary information about the severity of each defect, integrating this data into the metadata. The metadata will include details such as GPS coordinates and other relevant information, which will then be provided to subsequent system modules. This comprehensive metadata delivery will enable efficient downstream processing and decision-making within the system.</p>
<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<pre> graph LR Input[Input Hardware: Drone, CCTV, Dash Camera Type: JPEG, PNG, MP4, RSTP STREAM] --> RDD[Road Defect Detection [Deep Learning Software System] Defects on the roads are detected.] RDD --> SA[Severity Assessment [Software System] A road's severity is assessed.] SA --> KB[(Kafka Broker [Container: Apache Kafka] Message bus)] KB --> TEKNIKER[TEKNIKER Task 5.4 [Software System] Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies] KB --> iDriving[iDriving UI [Software System] The project's graphical interface presents essential information.] </pre>
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>Current TRL: 4</p>

	Expected TRL: 6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deep learning models
Deployment Premises	-
Involved Partners	INFRAPLAN, TEKNIKER
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.3-1, TR-FUN-4.3-2

Table 28 - Weather Prediction Tool (WRF and Data Assimilation) – Architectural Design and Description

Weather Prediction Tool (WRF and Data Assimilation): Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures	
Description	This tool combines the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model with a data assimilation system (WRFDA) using Docker. It automates the entire forecasting process, from data pre-processing to assimilation of real-time observational data, and model execution. The tool supports multi-domain nesting and generates high-resolution weather predictions. The system also includes an API-based service for real-time weather data ingestion and an output verification module that compares model forecasts against ground truth data to ensure accuracy.

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<pre>graph LR; A[Weather station data management] --> B[Assimilating weather station Data for better accuracy]; B --> C[Model configuration 1st step. (Choice of Domains)]; C --> D[Model configuration 2nd step. (Determine operational flow and deploy docker containers for each case)]; D --> E[Post processing weather forecast model output]; E --> F[Weather Forecast Output validation];</pre>
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL 6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Docker• Git• Web Framework (ex. Django Rest Framework)• MPICH• NetCDF• WRF• WPS• WRFDA• Relational Database (SQL)• Python
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>DREVEN in house servers</p>

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Involved Partners	DREVEN
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.4-1/TR-FUN-4.4-2/TR-FUN-4.4-3

Table 29 - AI-Based Real-Time Weather Alert System – Architectural Design and Description

AI-Based Real-Time Weather Alert System: Smart Environmental Condition Monitoring for Proactive Road Safety Measures	
Description	<p>This system enables real-time and forecast-based environmental monitoring by integrating station observations and weather model predictions. Data is made accessible for specific geographic areas, and an automated process (scheduled via cron) checks if predefined hazard thresholds are met. The outcomes are processed by an AI engine (LLM), which generates alerts enriched with risk levels and weather-related data. These alerts are then served through an API, making them available to the iDriving platform for enhanced decision-making and road safety measures.</p>
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<pre> graph LR subgraph Periodical_Execution [Periodical Execution] A[Retrieval of forecasts from external sources] B[Generation of current weather data (nowcast)] C[Discrete Locations] D[Threshold Mechanism for hazard identification] E{Threshold exceeded} F[AI generated hazard alert] end A --> D B --> D C --> D D --> E E --> F F --> G[Accessed via API] </pre>

Expected TRL	TRL 6
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Python• Docker• Git• Django Rest Framework• Relational Database (e.g., PostgreSQL)• Open Source or Cloud-Based LLM (via API access)
Deployment Premises	DREVEN in-house servers or Cloud infrastructure
Involved Partners	DREVEN
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4.4-4

Table 30 - 3D-Smart Tool – Architectural Design and Description

3D-Smart Tool: AI-driven 3D Scene Generation for Safety & Maintenance Monitoring	
Description	The tool aims to transform visual data from road environments into 3D representations, integrating it into the iDriving ecosystem for improved safety, maintenance insights and incident/progress monitoring. This involves acquiring data using UAVs, processing it using Neural Radiance Fields or Gaussian Splatting, and enhancing iDriving's ability to detect and assess road hazards, improving situational awareness and remote responses for road managers.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<pre> graph TD subgraph Input A[UAV footage] B[Ground-based moving camera] C[Input images from T4.3] end Input --> D[Preprocess Visual Data [Structure from Motion Software System] Camera pose and parameters are estimated] D --> E[Scene Reconstruction [Training Software System] 3D scenes parameters are optimized] E --> F[3D Render [Software System] 3D scene visualization-navigation] F --> G[(Kafka Broker [Container: Apache Kafka] Message Bus)] G --> H[Tekniker Task 5.4 [Software System] AI Optimized Maintenance Through Digital Twin] G --> I[SImavi Task 5.5 [Software System] Digital Twin-Based Control Center] </pre>
Expected TRL	TRL 6
Technologies	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the 3D-Smart Tool:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3D Gaussian Splatting ● Neural Radiance Field

Deployment Premises	-
Involved Partners	ACCELIGENCE, TEKNIKER, SIMAVI
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-4-5

Table 31 - Dynamic Monitoring Platform – Architectural Design and Description

Expected TRL	TRL 6
Technologies	The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the Dynamic Update of Criteria Catalogue Component: 1. Python Learning models
Deployment Premises	-
Involved Partners	-
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.1-1 TR-FUN-5.1-2, TR-FUN-5.1-3,

Table 32 - SUMO: Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems – Architectural Design and Description

SUMO: Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems	
Description	The tool aims to simulate and analyse intermodal traffic systems, integrating road vehicles, public transport, and pedestrians for enhanced traffic management. By utilizing real-world traffic data, road topology, and SUMO add-ons like VANETT for telecommunications, it enables detailed traffic flow simulation, risk prediction, and hazard assessment. The platform supports real-time and large-scale simulations, requiring computational resources based on service levels, making it a valuable tool for optimizing urban mobility and safety.

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Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)

Expected TRL

TRL 6

Technologies

The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the SUMO: Digital Twin Component:

2. Sumo for traffic simulation of use case networks
3. Python for Safety assessment
4. Learning algorithms (Deep learning/ statistical methods)

Geojson for safety alerts

Deployment Premises

-

Involved Partners	TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.3-*

Table 33 - CARLA: Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems – Architectural Design and Description

CARLA: Digital Twin Powered Predictive Safety Measures and Warning Systems	
Description	The tool aims to simulate and analyse traffic environments in 3D, providing insights for autonomous driving systems. By integrating real-world traffic data, road types, and obstacles, it enables risk prediction and hazard visualization.

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Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL 6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the CARLA: Digital Twin Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CARLA for simulation of monitored areas ● Developments in Python for Safety assessment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Trajectory recognition and processing ▪ Training Deep learning/ statistical models ▪ Evaluation of the models
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>-</p>

iDRIVING

**Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles
Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies**

Involved Partners	TUC
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.3-*

Table 34 - AI-Optimized Maintenance Through Digital Twin – Architectural Design and Description

AI-Optimized Maintenance Through Digital Twin: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies	
Description	<p>This overarching tool aims to develop a dynamic risk management system for maintenance optimization based on cost, risk, and health modelling. It leverages a Digital Twin to enable real-time decision-making and ensure optimal safety conditions at a viable cost. It combines risk assessment, health evaluation, and maintenance scheduling to support proactive and cost-effective strategies.</p>
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<p>The tool is composed of three subcomponents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Module 1.1: Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool – Risk computation via FMEA • Module 1.2: Health and Logistics Management Tool – Integrates Road condition, weather, and traffic models • Module 1.3: Maintenance Scheduling Tool – Short and long-term scheduling based on risk/health data <p>Each module interacts through a shared infrastructure</p> <div style="text-align: center; border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 15px; padding: 10px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p>AI-Optimized Maintenance Through Digital Twin</p> <pre> graph LR M1[Module 1.1 Risk Assessment] --> M2[Module 1.2 Health & Logistics] M2 --> M3[Module 1.3 Maintenance Schedule] M2 --> M1 M3 --> M1 </pre> </div>
Expected TRL	TRL 5–6
Technologies	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of this component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital twin platforms for infrastructure • Condition monitoring and predictive models • Risk analysis (FMEA) • Metaheuristic optimization models • Simulation engines for planning • Data integration APIs (traffic, weather) <p>The technologies are defined through the three modules outlined below, within the specific details of each submodule.</p>
Deployment Premises	<p>Deployed in environments where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time and historical data from road infrastructure is available.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weather and traffic data can be integrated. Simulation and optimization engines can be executed for decision support. <p>The tool can be installed on local servers or accessed via secure web interfaces.</p>
Involved Partners	INFRAPLAN, CERTH, UNIV-EIFFEL, SIMAVI
Involved Partners	INFRAPLAN, CERTH, UNIV-EIFFEL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.4-1 to TR-FUN-5.4-3 (distributed across the 3 modules, specific details below)

Table 35 - Dynamic Risk Assessment Module – Architectural Design and Description

Dynamic Risk Assessment Tool: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies	
Description	This tool introduces a dynamic risk calculation methodology that goes beyond traditional static models, integrating real-time data (road and traffic characteristics) and support logistics and maintenance planning.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	<p>The architecture of Module 1.1 consists of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Risk assessment: the central engine to compute risk using FMEA methodology. Scenario Model & Risk Simulation: it simulates different what-if scenarios to assess how risk levels would evolve under changing conditions.

	<p>These components receive input from key data sources: Road characteristics, Traffic inputs and Vulnerability data.</p> <p>The output- risk metrics and scenario results – is shared with Tool 1.2 (for logistic planning) and Module 1.3 (for maintenance scheduling)</p>
Expected TRL	TRL 5-6
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk modelling from FMEA- python • Scenario simulation- python • Visualization and Dashboard- Grafana, Power BI
Deployment Premises	The tool can be installed on local servers or accessed via secure web interfaces.
Involved Partners	TEKNIKER, INFRA PLAN
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.4-1: The risk assessment engine must calculate the risk for each infrastructure segment.

Table 36 - Health and Logistics Management Module – Architectural Design and Description

Health And logistics Management Tool: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies	
Description	This tool integrates condition monitoring, weather forecasting, and traffic data to enable efficient logistics and maintenance planning. It supports predictive maintenance through Digital Twin simulation and ensures optimal resource allocation to minimize infrastructure degradation.

Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)

The architecture consists of three layers:

- Input sources: condition monitoring (RCI, Health Index), weather forecasts, and traffic forecasts.
- Data Integration Layer: performs ETL and synchronization of input data.
- Health & Logistics Layer: integrates predictive models to compute health indexes, assess road condition, and support logistics planning via a dedicated dashboard.

Outputs feed Module 1.1 (for risk analysis) and Module 1.3 (for scheduling).

Expected TRL	TRL 5-6
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Index Calculation- Python with data science libraries (NumPy, SciPy, Scikit-learn). • Visualization and Dashboard- Grafana, Power BI
Deployment Premises	Operable either in a local server or via cloud/web interface.
Involved Partners	INFRAPLAN, CERTH, UNIV-EIFFEL, SIMAVI
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.4-2: The system must compute dynamic the health index or Road Condition Index values.

Table 37 - Maintenance Scheduling Tool – Architectural Design and Description

Maintenance Scheduling Tool: Digital Twin machine consulting for Proactive and Cost-Effective Maintenance Strategies	
Description	This tool defines optimal short- and long-term maintenance tasks using data from Tools 1.1 and 1.2. It uses optimization algorithms to balance risk, cost, and resource availability, producing actionable scheduling plans for immediate and strategic maintenance.
Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)	The architecture of Module 1.3 is centred around the Scheduling Engine that generates short-term and long-term maintenance plans. It receives input from three main sources: Module 1.1, Module 1.2 and predefined maintenance plans or constraints. It processes this information to produce detailed Task Plans (list of prioritized maintenance actions, suggested execution dates, required resources and estimated costs for each intervention or group of actions).
Expected TRL	TRL 5-6
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic scheduling algorithms - python • Optimization algorithms (metaheuristics)- python • Cost and prioritization models- python
Deployment Premises	The tool can be installed on local servers or accessed via secure web interfaces.
Involved Partners	INFRA PLAN, SIMAVI, CERTH, UNIV-EIFFEL
Related Technical requirements	TR-FUN-5.4-3: The scheduling engine must generate short term plan and long-term planning using optimization algorithms.

Table 38 - Digital Twin-Based Control Centre – Architectural Design and Description

Digital Twin-Based Control Centre: Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness	
Description	A control centre that integrates the Digital Twin concept with extended reality.

<p>Architectural Diagram and Subcomponents (components View)</p>	<pre> graph TD User[iDriving User [Person]] --> Auth[Authentication module [Service: e.g. Unity] Supports the authentication process of the user.] Auth --> UI[UI module [Service: e.g. Unity] Display the output of the related services, relevant messages for the user.] Auth --> Comm[Communication module [Service: e.g. Unity] Enables the communication with the backend.] Comm --> Messages[Messages module [Service: e.g. Unity] Processes the information received from the backend and prepares it for the frontend.] Messages --> UI subgraph Frontend [Frontend [Digital Twin-Based Control Center]] Auth UI Messages end Backend[Backend [Server: e.g. Kafka] Supports the authentication process, messaging system.] Frontend <--> rest API Backend </pre>
<p>Expected TRL</p>	<p>TRL6</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>The following technologies will be used for the implementation of the X Component:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unity • C# • REST API • Photoshop • Blender 3D
<p>Deployment Premises</p>	<p>Laptop (Windows), XR glasses</p>
<p>Involved Partners</p>	<p>INTRA, INFRA PLAN, ALP.LAB, AIM, DREVEN, THESSALONIKI</p>
<p>Related Technical requirements</p>	<p>TR-FUN-5.5-1, TR-FUN-5.5-2, TR-FUN-5.5-3</p>

5.5 iDRIVING Process Views

The following section presents component-level flow diagrams in the form of system sequence diagrams, contributed by all partners. Each diagram illustrates the runtime interaction between key elements of the respective component. A brief description accompanies each diagram to clarify its purpose and integration within the iDRIVING architecture.

5.5.1 Tekniker Dataspace Connector

A modular solution that allows organizations to establish a single point of entry for accessing and exchanging data within a data space. It ensures interoperability in data sharing, fosters trust among participants, and guarantees data sovereignty throughout its entire lifecycle.

Figure 11 - Tekniker dataspace connector sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 11:

1. The Data Owner defines their data catalog:
 - a. Brief catalog description
 - b. Catalog location (DataService)
 - c. List of datasets:
 - i. Dataset location (DataAddress)
 - ii. Data type (Distribution)
 - iii. Access policies (Offer)
2. The Data User requests the catalog
3. The Data User's connector initiates the Catalog Protocol
4. The Data User receives and accepts the catalog's access policies (Contract Negotiation Protocol)
 - a. Both parties can monitor the contract negotiation process
5. The Data User requests a dataset → the Transfer Process Protocol starts
6. Data transfer depends on the chosen method (PUSH or PULL):
 - a. PULL: Processing tools access the data directly
 - b. PUSH: Data is delivered to a defined location via the processing tools

5.5.2 Route Guidance tool

Description of the sequence diagram: The process starts with sensors (cameras, GPS, road sensors, etc.) detecting incidents, congestion, or hazardous conditions. This data is analysed by the relative iDriving component, which extracts key traffic parameters. The results are communicated to the ITMS which then evaluates the situation and determines optimal traffic management strategies (based on the simulated scenarios), such as dynamic signal adjustments and route recommendations based on vehicle type. The system communicates with traffic signals to implement changes and provides guidance to road users (drivers, truck drivers, motorcyclists, cyclists) through the iDriving user communication channels (app, in-vehicle etc.). In critical situations, an Emergency Response System is also triggered for emergency vehicle drivers to ensure timely intervention.

Figure 12 - Route Guidance tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 12:

1. Receive input: Data from various sources is collected and processed by the relative iDriving components. Useful information regarding actual or imminent traffic congestion is extracted and provided to the route guidance algorithm as input.
2. Historical data of travel demand, traffic congestion, traffic signal settings and other network-related information will be used for conducting SUMO microscopic simulation tests

3. Alerts and warnings about identified incidents (e.g. accidents, loopholes or infrastructure failure, fallen trees, extreme weather conditions) at specific location and time in the network (road, lane), which are provided by the relative iDriving tools, are given as input to the routing algorithm. The type, location and time of the incident are communicated.
4. All input data are introduced in the SUMO simulation environment of the respective traffic network (town/city) under consideration. Incident location is used to define the affected area. Traffic congestion levels, potentially hazardous weather conditions (e.g. wind, flooding, storm, infrastructure failure etc.) are used to estimate the value of a risk function for every link in the affected area per vehicle type.
5. Paths of all trips that are crossing the affected area are recalculated by the Route Guidance Tool's algorithms, based on the current vehicle location and its destination. Alternative paths are decided so that the total risk level of all used paths is minimized among alternative options.
6. Alternative paths are communicated to the respective vehicles, through the relative iDriving communication components.

5.5.3 Signal Control Tool

Figure 13 - Signal Control tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 13:

1. Receive input: Data from various sources (e.g. cameras, GPS, and loop detectors) is collected and processed by the relative iDriving components.
2. Detection: Useful information regarding detected vehicles at intersections and/or queue length estimation at intersections per link, is provided to the signal control algorithm as input.
3. Signal Control Module: The module is introduced in the SUMO simulation environment with the appropriate historical data of travel demand, traffic congestion, traffic signal settings and other network-related information, to be used for conducting SUMO microscopic simulation tests. According to the number of vehicles waiting in the queues, traffic light splits are computed and broadcasted to the traffic lights.
4. Export: Finally, during the export, traffic light splits are stored in appropriate output files.

5.5.4 Mobile Application & In-Vehicle Application

Figure 14 - Mobile Application & In-Vehicle Application sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 14:

1. Preparation: Mobile/in-vehicle application is deployed on the mobile device and running properly.

2. Connection: Mobile/in-vehicle application is connected to the internet and to the server.
3. Send/receive: Mobile/in-vehicle application sends/receives messages for different situations.
4. Server/Message bus: Server/Message bus sends/receives information.

5.5.5 Aerial Surveillance UAV System

Deliver a reconfigurable UAV system equipped with different sensors and cameras to enable precise, efficient data collection from areas of interest on demand or in real time. This task aims to develop a UAV capable of autonomous navigation and real-time decision-making, particularly in complex environments such as maintenance operations and incident monitoring. By leveraging AI, advanced algorithms, and the unique capabilities of each UAV, the system will ensure a swift, accurate, and effective response to various road situations.

Figure 15 - Aerial Surveillance UAV System sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 15:

1. Prepare UAV Autonomous Flight: The UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) system is prepared for deployment, ensuring that the drone is operational, and all required parameters are set.
2. Drone Ready for Autonomous Flight: The UAV undergoes final system checks, including battery level, GPS calibration, and communication with the control platform.
3. Deploy UAV: The UAV takes off and begins patrolling the defined area.
4. The UAV Captures the required information such as maintenance operations and incident monitoring based on the selected sensors (RGB / Thermal cameras).
5. Image / Video Processing Using the Developed AI Algorithms
6. The platform receives information regarding any maintenance operations and incident monitoring.

5.5.6 Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage

This component provides an AI-powered service for generating optimal flight paths for a single or multiple UAVs to cooperatively cover large offshore areas. It takes as input a geospatial area (in WGS84 format) and UAV parameters, and generates energy-aware, overlap-free trajectories. The paths account for obstacles, no-fly zones, and individual UAV constraints (e.g., battery, max range). The service is integrated into an end-to-end platform, where the frontend collects mission definitions and the backend processes them to deliver mission-ready flight plans in standard formats.

Figure 16 - Autonomous UAV Deployment for Area Coverage sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 16:

1. Input Source

The input to the tool is a user-defined mission area, represented as a polygon in WGS84 coordinates, optionally including no-fly zones and static obstacles. Additionally, UAV specifications such as battery level, flight time, altitude limits, speed, and camera field-of-view (FoV) are required.

2. Data Processing

The system parses and validates the geospatial input and UAV parameters. It then computes an optimal coverage path for either a single UAV or multiple UAVs based on the mission definition. Obstacles and no-fly zones are factored into the path planning algorithm to ensure legal and safe flight operations.

In the case of multi-UAV operations, the system distributes sub-areas and computes coordinated coverage paths to ensure complete and efficient mission execution.

3. Output Source

A standardized .JSON file is generated that includes:

- The computed waypoints for each UAV (if multi-UAV)
- Area and obstacles/No-Fly zones (if any) definitions
- Mission parameters

5.5.7 Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool

Figure 17 - Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 17:

1. Input Source

- The module receives data from street or drone cameras.
- Input can be either individual frames or video streams.

2. Data Processing

- A deep learning model detects traffic violations, including:
 - o Drivers not wearing seatbelts
 - o Drivers using mobile phones
 - o Bikers not wearing helmets
 - Each frame is processed to detect relevant objects, with output including
 - o Object class
 - o Confidence score
 - o Bounding box coordinates
3. Metadata Generation
A JSON file is created containing metadata for each detected object. The system also counts the number of detected cars per frame and exports this information.
4. Output Generation
The processed frames or video are forwarded to the iDriving UI. Detection results (objects and metadata) are also sent to TEKNIKER for further processing in the activity recognition task.

5.5.8 License Plate Detection Tool

Figure 18 - License Plate Detection Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 18:

1. Input Source
The input source for this tool is the same as the detection tool—frames from street cameras or drone cameras.
2. Data Processing
The tool processes the frame simultaneously with the detection module. It focuses on identifying vehicle license plates and extracting their numbers. Once a license plate is detected, it links this information to the

corresponding offending vehicle (e.g., not wearing a seatbelt, using a phone, etc.).

3. Metadata Generation

The output is a JSON file containing the license plate numbers of the offending vehicles, along with relevant metadata.

4. Output

A JSON file is generated that includes the license plates of all identified offending vehicles in the processed frame.

5.5.9 Helmet Detection Tool

Figure 19 - Helmet Detection Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 19:

1. Input Source

- The module receives data from street or drone cameras.
- Input can be either individual frames or video streams.

2. Data Processing

- A deep learning model detects traffic violation (bikers not wearing helmets)
- Simultaneously we detect the license plate of each offender
- We combine the information of the vehicle and the license plate

3. Metadata Generation

- A JSON file is created containing metadata for each detected object.

4. Output

The processed frames or video are forwarded to the iDriving UI.

Detection results (objects and metadata) are also sent to TEKNIKER for further processing in the activity recognition task.

5.5.10 Zebra Crossing Detection Tool

Figure 20 - Zebra Crossing Detection Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 20:

1. Input Source
 - The module receives data from street or drone cameras.
 - Input can be either individual frames or video streams.
2. Data Processing
 - A deep learning model is detecting the zebra crossing
3. Metadata Generation
 - A JSON file is generated with the coordinates of the Zebra Crossing
4. Output
 - We forward the coordinates of the object to TEKNIKER, so they can combine the data and determine whether a person is walking on it

5.5.11 Fallen Tree and Rockslide Detection Tool

Figure 21 - Fallen Tree and Rockslide Detection Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 21:

1. Input Source
 - The module receives data from drone cameras.
 - Input can be either individual frames or video streams.
2. Data Processing
 - A deep learning model is used to detect rockslides or fallen trees within the frame
3. Metadata Generation
 - A JSON file is created containing metadata for each detected object.
4. Output
 - The processed frames or video are forwarded to the iDriving UI.
 - Detection results (objects and metadata) are also sent to the End Users

5.5.12 Crashed Vehicle Detection Tool

Figure 22 - Crashed Vehicle Detection Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 22:

1. Input Source
 - The module receives data from drone cameras.
 - Input can be either individual frames or video streams.
2. Data Processing
 - A deep learning model is used to detect crashed cars within the frame
3. Metadata Generation
 - A JSON file is created containing metadata for each detected object.
4. Output
 - The processed frames or video are forwarded to the iDriving UI.
 - Detection results (objects and metadata) are also sent to the End Users

5.5.13 Red Light Violation Detector

Figure 23 - Red Light Violation Detector sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 23:

This will represent the flow between components step-by-step, such as:

1. Camera sends video stream
2. Detection module identifies vehicle
3. Tracking module follows vehicle
4. Logic engine checks line crossing
5. Verifies red light timing
6. Generates violation event
7. Exports image + metadata

5.5.14 Improper Lane Usage Detector

Figure 24 - Improper Lane Usage Detector sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 24:

1. Camera sends video frames
2. Detection Module identifies vehicles
3. Tracking Module generates trajectories
4. Logic Engine:
 - Compares trajectory with allowed zones
 - Applies zone-specific rules (e.g., no entry, wrong direction)
 - Triggers violation if needed
5. Export Layer stores metadata

5.5.15 Zebra Crossing Violation Detector

Figure 25 - Zebra Crossing Violation Detector sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 25:

1. Video stream received: the system receives frames from recorded camera feed.
2. Pedestrian detection & tracking: Pedestrian are detected in each frame and assigned unique tracking ID
3. Zebra crossing segmentation: the crosswalk area is identified.
4. Violation analysis: the pedestrian's location is compared to zebra crossing zone using spatial logic.
5. Violation event generation: if improper behaviour is detected, the violation is triggered.
6. Evidence logging: metadata (timestamp, pedestrian ID, and zone info) can be saved or send.

5.5.16 Abrupt Movement Detector

Figure 26 - Abrupt Movement Detector sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 26:

1. Vehicle Sensors → Data Acquisition Module: *Send raw sensor data (acceleration, angular velocity, GPS position) in real time.*
2. Data Acquisition Module → Preprocessing Module: *Provide synchronized and timestamped data streams.*
3. Preprocessing Module → Anomaly Detection Module: *Send filtered, noise-reduced data ready for analysis.*
4. Anomaly Detection Module → Event Logger (only if anomaly detected): *Trigger anomaly detected event with type (acceleration, braking, steering, trajectory), timestamp, and data snapshot.*
5. Event Logger → Local Server Database: *Store event log with metadata (event type, timestamp, sensor data, GPS position)*

5.5.17 Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool

Figure 27 - Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 27:

1. Accept Input Sources
 - The module receives input from various sources, including drone cameras, fixed traffic cameras, and dashboard cameras in vehicles.
2. Select and Process Input
 - After selecting the appropriate source, the module feeds the data into a deep learning model designed to detect road defects such as potholes and cracks.
3. Generate Output
 - The model processes the input images and outputs annotated images, marking defect locations with bounding boxes.
 - Simultaneously, the same information is formatted as JSON text, which includes metadata like GPS coordinates (if provided by the original source).
4. Assess Defect Severity
 - The processed data is sent to the severity assessment module, where each defect's severity is estimated.
5. Forward Results to UI
 - Finally, all results, along with severity assessments, are sent to subsequent modules and integrated into the project's UI, where they are presented.

5.5.18 Weather Prediction Tool (WRF and Data Assimilation)

Figure 28 - Weather Prediction Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 28:

1. Set Up Environment
Deploy WRF and WRFDA within a Docker container for easy management and portability.
2. Data Preparation
Gather meteorological data (e.g., GFS, observational data) required for initial conditions and boundary conditions.
3. Data Assimilation
Use WRFDA to integrate real-time observational data into the model, improving initial conditions for better forecast accuracy.
4. Run Weather Prediction
Execute WRF model using the prepared input data and assimilated fields for weather prediction.
5. Post-Processing
Generate forecasts and relevant meteorological outputs (e.g., precipitation, temperature) for analysis and decision-making.
6. Verification
Compare model outputs with real-time data to ensure forecast quality and accuracy.

5.5.19 AI-Based Real-Time Weather Alert System

Figure 29 - AI-Based Real-Time Weather Alert System sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 29:

1. Forecast & Nowcast Retrieval

Collect forecast data from external sources and generate current (nowcast) weather data.

2. Location-Based Filtering

Extract and organize data for predefined discrete locations of interest (e.g., cities, road segments).

3. Hazard Identification

Apply threshold-based rules to detect potential hazards based on forecast and real-time data.

4. AI-Driven Alert Generation

If thresholds are exceeded, feed the event into an AI model (LLM) which creates a context-aware hazard alert.

5. Alert Delivery

Alerts are exposed via a REST API and can be accessed in real time by the iDriving platform or other systems.

5.5.20 3D-SMART Tool

Figure 30 - 3D-SMART Tool sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 30:

1. The tool proposes the UAV's path based on the target area's extent, ensuring that the scene will be captured from all possible viewpoints.
2. Raw data acquired from the UAV is extracted, processed, and formatted before being fed into the model.
3. The model receives the processed data, optimizes its parameters, and transforms the 2D data into a highly detailed 3D environment
4. Realistic 3D renders or gaussian splats in ply format can be extracted.

5.5.21 ClaireSITI Platform

Figure 31 - ClaireSITI Platform sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 31:

1. Access data from use cases

- Collect data from each use cases (UAVs, weather stations, AI camera outputs) based on SCC requirements
- 2. Process to the computation of KPI based on new data collected
- 3. Update SCC formula/parameters through continuous learning of KPI
- 4. store KPI send updates for all partners or road managers through frontend dashboard or geojson

5.5.22 SUMO (Simulation of Urban Mobility)

Provide alerts and safety measures based on a digital twin built using the SUMO simulator. The tool is designed to simulate various transport scenarios using historical data and real-time field data (UAVs, cameras, sensors) to anticipate risks for different road users and deliver alerts or safety measures to users and network managers.

Figure 32 - SUMO sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 32:

1. Access data from monitored areas
 - a. Collect data from edge sensors (UAVs, weather stations, AI camera outputs) to adapt traffic scenarios based on real-time data.
2. Access historical data for traffic calibration
 - a. Use historical data to determine initial traffic demand across the network, including areas outside monitored zones.
3. Simulate traffic scenarios in SUMO
 - a. Perform a simulation of road users in SUMO, integrating both historical demand and real-time data. SUMO also integrates

communication tools to simulate various scenarios according to road user compliances to IDriving systems and communication delays

4. Process safety assessment on simulated data
 - a. Extract safety features from simulated data—such as user trajectories and behaviours—to compute safety measures or alerts.
5. Provide geolocated alerts and measures
 - a. Send safety measures, alerts, or risk assessments across the network based on infrastructure type, formatted as GeoJSON.

5.5.23 CARLA (Autonomous Driving Simulation Platform)

Provide alerts and safety measures based on a digital twin built using CARLA and SUMO simulators to ensure a 3D representation on monitored area. The tool is designed to simulate various transport scenarios using historical data and real-time field data (UAVs, cameras, sensors) to anticipate risks for multiple road users (car, pedestrian, cyclist) and deliver alerts or safety measures to users and network managers.

Figure 33 - CARLA sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 33:

1. Access data from monitored areas
 - a. Get data from on edge sensors (UAV, weather station, IA camera outputs) to detect incoming road user on the monitored area
2. Access historical data for traffic calibration
 - a. Historical data provides initial demands of the whole network outside monitored areas
3. Simulate in 3D road user behaviours on CARLA and SUMO

- a. Realise a 3D simulation of the monitored areas in use cases based on incoming road users and historical demands. Various road user characteristics (aggressive, risky) can be provided for simulation.
4. Process safety assessment on simulated data
 - a. Extract safety features from simulated data – user trajectories, behaviours – to compute safety measures or alerts
5. Provide alerts and measures
 - a. Interact with roads users on site with safety measures by providing potential risks

5.5.24 AI-Optimized Maintenance through Digital Twin

Consists of:

- Module 1.1: Dynamic Risk Assessment
- Module 1.2: Health and Logistics Management
- Module 1.3: Maintenance Scheduling

The system relies on a shared infrastructure and data pipelines to support decision-making in near real-time.

Global Component Sequence Overview

Figure 34 - AI-Optimized Maintenance through Digital Twin - Global Component sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 34

Data flow and Module interactions:

1. Sensor Network collects real-time data like condition, weather, and traffic, and sends it to Module 1.2 (Health & Logistics Management).
2. Module 1.2 performs data processing (ETL) and computes health indices (like RCI and HI), then displays this info on the Dashboard.
3. Module 1.2 also sends processed health and vulnerability data to Module 1.1 (Dynamic Risk Assessment), which:
 - Calculates risks using methods like FMEA.
 - Runs simulations (e.g., “what if” scenarios).
 - Outputs result to the Dashboard (e.g., risk maps).
4. Module 1.1 passes risk and scenario data to Module 1.3 (Maintenance Scheduling), while Module 1.2 also provides logistics info.
5. Module 1.3 combines inputs to generate short- and long-term maintenance plans, cost estimates, and priority lists—also visualized on the Dashboard.

Module 1.1 Risk Assessment

Figure 35 - AI-Optimized Maintenance through Digital Twin – Module 1.1 Risk Assessment sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 35:

1. Receive data from Module 1.2: Inputs include the Health Index, traffic, road, and vulnerability information.
2. Compute Risk using FMEA Methodology: Module 1.1 uses Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) to assess potential risks and their impact.
3. Run Scenario Simulation – What-if Engine: It simulates various hypothetical conditions to test system resilience and response under different stressors.
4. Generate Risk Metrics: Outputs include quantifiable risk values, rankings, or categories that can inform decision-making.
5. Expose REST API to Dashboard: Module 1.1 shares results via an API, enabling integration and real-time access.
6. Dashboard displays risk maps and simulations: The frontend/dashboard visualizes these insights for users—e.g., risk heatmaps, simulation outcomes.

Module 1.2 Health & Logistics Management

Figure 36 - AI-Optimized Maintenance through Digital Twin – Module 1.2 Health & Logistics Management sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 36:

1. Get External Forecasts: Module 1.2 receives weather and traffic forecasts from external APIs.
2. Step 2: Stream Sensor Data: It simultaneously ingests real-time condition data from on-field sensors (e.g., pavement RCI).

3. ETL Processing: Extraction of raw data, Transformation (cleaning, normalization), Loading and integration into its system
4. Predictive Modelling: It runs machine learning models to compute a Health Index for each road segment.
5. Send to Dashboard: The final output—road condition forecasts and Health Index—is pushed to the dashboard for end-user visualization.

Module 1.3 Maintenance Scheduling

Figure 37 - AI-Optimized Maintenance through Digital Twin - Module 1.3 Maintenance Scheduling sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 37:

1. Step 1: Input from Module 1.1
Receives risk levels and scenario outputs that indicate potential failure zones and risk-critical areas.
2. Step 2: Input from Module 1.2
Gets logistics and condition metrics, including road degradation, accessibility, and available resources.
3. Step 3: Optimization Engine

Uses metaheuristic algorithms (e.g., genetic algorithms, simulated annealing) to compute optimized scheduling strategies.

4. Step 4: Generate Maintenance Plans

Creates both short-term (urgent or minor fixes) and long-term (strategic upgrades) task plans.

5. Step 5: Output to Dashboard

Exports task lists in CSV/JSON formats, including costs, resource needs, and priorities, which are then visualized on the dashboard.

5.5.25 Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness

Figure 38 - Digital Twin-Based Control Centre with XR features for Enhanced Situational Awareness sequence diagram

Sequence diagram steps, presented in Figure 38:

1. Preparation: Dashboard is deployed on the mobile device and running properly
2. Connection: Dashboard is connected to the internet and to the server.
3. Send/receive: Dashboard sends/receives messages for different situations.
4. Server/Message bus: Server/Message bus sends/receives information.
5. Dashboard: Generate and display statistics for road managers.

6 Conclusion / Future Work

This deliverable has defined the technical requirements and provided a high-level architectural overview of the iDriving digital ecosystem, building on the consolidated user requirements and pilot scenarios established earlier in the project. The iDriving system is designed as an integrated, modular platform supporting real-time road safety monitoring, data-driven decision support, and predictive maintenance through advanced sensing, edge computing, AI analytics, and Digital Twin technologies.

The requirements identified herein are divided into functional and non-functional categories, reflecting both the operational needs of the various pilot sites and the technical challenges of implementing a pan-European road safety platform. Functional requirements are grouped according to the system's major building blocks, as structured by Work Packages 3, 4, and 5, with special attention paid to ensuring traceability from user needs and use cases to concrete system features. Non-functional requirements (quality attributes) have also been documented to guide the system's evolution and ensure compliance with relevant standards and regulations.

The architecture presented follows the C4 Model, supporting clear communication at multiple levels of abstraction and illustrating the interactions among system components, data flows, and external actors. The mapping of requirements to system architecture ensures that the iDriving platform remains flexible, extensible, and capable of meeting the diverse operational contexts found across the project's pilot sites.

The technical specifications provided in this report, serve as the foundational reference for the ongoing design, development, and integration activities in subsequent work packages. As implementation progresses and feedback from pilot deployments is gathered, it is anticipated that some requirements or architectural details may be refined or updated to address emerging insights or evolving operational needs. Throughout this process, the project will maintain a strong focus on traceability, stakeholder engagement, and compliance with ethical and regulatory requirements.

In summary, this deliverable sets the groundwork for the realization of the iDriving vision: leveraging next-generation digital infrastructure and intelligent systems to improve road safety, resilience, and operational efficiency across European transport networks.

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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

7 PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

iDriving Consortium

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